

ISW

In Silico World: Lowering barriers to ubiquitous adoption of In Silico Trials
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D9.1 Legal and ethical inventory

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Executive summary

The present Deliverable 'D9.1 – Legal and Ethical Inventory', part of Work Package 9 'Ethical and Legal Framework' of the In Silico World project, provides an overview of the **core pieces of legislation and ethical principles that are relevant to the In Silico project, and thus, in silico trials.**

The analysis finds the following areas of legislation are of relevance:

- **Privacy and Data Protection:** The data processed for *in silico* trials entail the processing of personal data of individuals (notably, patients) in healthcare settings. As a consequence, privacy and data protection legislation becomes relevant. Privacy and data protection are distinct fundamental rights enshrined in the European Union's (EU) treaties. The core and directly applicable regulation concerning the processing of personal data is the General Data Protection Legislation (GDPR). Other important data protection initiatives are undertaken by the Council of Europe and the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD).
- **Data Governance:** In healthcare and *in silico* trials, the sharing of data across healthcare facilities may be considered a key factor for the development, testing, and validation of *in silico* models. The European legislator's and national Member States' growing interest in regulating data sharing has resulted in a new and rapidly evolving framework concerning the governance of data. The current EU legal framework on data governance includes the Open Data Directive, the Free Flow of Non-Personal Data Regulation, and the Data Governance Act. In addition to these, two legislative proposals are expected to radically change data sharing in the healthcare sector: the Data Act and the European Health Data Space.
- **Clinical Trials:** The legislation and regulatory documentation concerning clinical trials are relevant to the very essence of *in silico* trials. One of the main barriers envisaged by the In Silico World project is the lack of clear regulatory pathways for *in silico* trials. Illustrating the clinical trials' fundamental pieces of legislation in Europe is crucial for the project's objectives. The most relevant items of clinical trials legislation in the EU include the Declaration of Helsinki, the Declaration of Taipei, the Clinical Trials Directive, the Good Clinical Practice Directive, and the Clinical Trials Regulation.
- **Medical Devices and Medicinal Products:** From a product regulation perspective, *in silico* trials encompass medical devices and medicinal products. Concerning the first, the Medical Device Regulation and the In Vitro Medical Device Regulation are of primary importance, unitedly with the EU-level relevant bodies' guidance issued by the Medical Device Coordination Group. Concerning medicinal products, the analysis includes the Community Code for Medicinal Products for Human Use Directive 2009/94, the Advanced Therapeutic Medicinal Product Regulation, and the Health Technology Assessment Regulation.
- **Artificial Intelligence (AI):** It is no surprise that a fundamental component of *in silico* trials is artificial intelligence. The EU legal framework on Artificial Intelligence is in the process of being established. After the White Paper on Artificial Intelligence and the Guidelines on Trustworthy elaborated by the EU High-Level Expert Group on AI, the piece to monitor in the following months is the Artificial Intelligence Act. This proposal, if approved, will apply directly to all the EU Member States, and it will include general provisions of relevance to healthcare (including, for instance, medical devices) and *in silico* trials.

In addition to the above pieces of legislation, the study outlines the framework for forthcoming **Ethics guidelines**. Based on a principlist approach, these guidelines propose the analysis of four main **Biomedical Ethics principles** – i.e. **autonomy, justice, beneficence, non-maleficence** – and the secondary principle of **responsibility**. These principles will ultimately be beneficial for studying the fundamental ethical principles that may be used as guidance for interpreting the law and supporting stakeholders to ensure the protection and advancement of human values in the context of *in silico* trials.

The deliverable provides a descriptive overview of the above mentioned legal frameworks. It is prodromic to the next phases of the WP9, where the analysis will adopt an evaluative approach on legislation (D9.2, D9.3) to ultimately result in policy recommendations (D9.4).

1. Introduction

Objectives

The purpose of this deliverable is twofold. First, this deliverable aims to **draw a legal inventory** comprising the most critical pieces of legislation applicable to *in silico* trials¹. Second, the deliverable seeks to illustrate the fundamental **ethical principles** that may be relevant for them.

Document outline

To achieve the above objectives, the deliverable is divided into seven main sections. Since *in silico* trials may involve (at least at their very initial stages) the processing of personal data, it is essential to map the most important references concerning privacy and data protection. Section 2, '**Privacy and Data Protection**', provides this mapping. Further to data protection, data sharing in healthcare is becoming increasingly crucial for reaching the full potential of *in silico* trials. Section 3, '**Data Governance**', treats this issue, and outlines the core aspects of the data economy regulation for the healthcare sector. Clinical trial legislation is the cornerstone of the present and future WP9 analysis. Therefore, section 4, 'Clinical Trials', deals with the fundamentals of clinical trial legislation. Section 5, '**Medical Devices and Medicinal Products**', illustrates the most relevant legal sources concerning medical devices and medicinal products. The inventory then treats the artificial intelligence regulation, as AI is an essential component for *in silico* trials. Section 6, '**Artificial Intelligence**', outlines the most recent policy developments concerning AI, unitedly with the ethical aspects promoted at the EU level. Finally, section 7, '**Ethics Principles**', identifies and focuses on the fundamental moral principles that may serve in the future ethical analysis for the In Silico World project and, thus, *in silico* trials.

2. Privacy and Data Protection

Introduction

Over the last decades, modern healthcare systems have undergone a radical change towards **personalised healthcare**.² In personalised healthcare, practitioners rely on predictive models and their accuracy for favouring an approach to meet individual patients' needs and thus reach a more granular level of treatment effectiveness.³ As they rely on predictive models and they are oriented to prediction, *in silico* trials may be considered as belonging to the objective of personalised healthcare.⁴ The activities of personalised healthcare and *in silico* trials entail the use of individual's personal data. Personal data are meant as any information related to an identified and identifiable natural person ('the data subject').⁵ The processing of personal data receives protection from the long-established EU legal framework on data protection in the EU. Such a legal framework is composed of a set of regulations, ranging from international instruments to EU primary and

¹ The present legal inventory is mostly focused on core legislative pieces of legislation concerning data, AI, and medical products legislation. Other aspects such as intellectual property and liability issues are not in the scope of the study.

² see Verhenneman G, 'The Patient's Right to Privacy and Autonomy against a Changing Healthcare Model' (KU Leuven Faculteit Rechtsgeleerdheid 2020); Hood L and Friend SH, 'Predictive, Personalized, Preventive, Participatory (P4) Cancer Medicine' (2011) 8 Nature Reviews Clinical Oncology 184.

³ Biasin E, 'Reconsidering the Conceptualisation of Accuracy as a Principle of Data Processing. Doctoral proposal' (January 2022), 15 [on file with author].

⁴ 'Personalised' in 'personalised healthcare' means meeting four P: personalised, predictive, preventive/pre-emptive, and participatory. In the context of personalised healthcare, these terms can be further contextualised as follows. Personalised: the healthcare system's approach is to meet individual patients' variations to reach a more granular level of treatment effectiveness. Predictive: it aims at mining and integrating patients' data to construct models that are predictive and actionable – for instance, a disease model. Preventive means that the system will lead to have new tools capable of providing new insights into prevention – to follow the disease example, these tools may be more efficient diagnostics and therapeutics. Finally, the fourth P (Participatory) implies an enhanced participation of patients in healthcare decision making, a sort of partnership to between the individual and healthcare professionals of the system.

⁵ For a more complete definition of 'personal data', see the GDPR, art 4.

secondary law to national law and recommendations provided by EU-level and national-level administrative authorities. The following sections will enlist the most relevant ones.

Legal Framework on Privacy and Data Protection

The European Convention on Human Rights

Overview

The **European Convention on Human Rights**⁶ (ECHR) is an international instrument adopted by the Council of Europe (CoE), which came into force on 3 September 1953. The Convention was the first instrument to enshrine several rights stated in the United Nations' (UN) Universal Declaration of Human Rights⁷ and make them binding. Since its adoption, the Convention has been amended by 16 protocols, which amended the convention framework with additional rights to the original version. As of 2021, the Council of Europe comprises 47 contracting Parties, 27 of which are EU Member States (MS). Contracting parties have an international obligation to comply with it.

The ECHR guarantees the right to life, the right to liberty and security, the right to a fair trial, **the right to respect private life and family life**, freedom of thought, conscience and religion, freedom of expression, freedom of assembly and association. It also prohibits torture, slavery and forced labour, punishment without law, and discrimination in the enjoyment of the rights and freedoms set in the Convention. The European Court of Human Rights (ECtHR) in Strasbourg ensures that the states observe their obligations under the Convention. The Court can consider complaints from individuals, groups of individuals, Non-Governmental Organisations (NGOs) or legal persons.

A number of law **cases** were brought to the ECtHR concerning **privacy as intertwined with the fundamental right to health**. The cases encompass issues about the confidentiality of personal information concerning health⁸, access to personal medical records⁹, patient's consent¹⁰, and data protection¹¹, as applied in healthcare.

Relevance to In Silico World

Amongst its provisions of particular relevance for ISW is Article 8 ECHR (right to respect for private and family life). Article 8 ECHR sets that everyone has the right to respect his private and family life, their home and correspondence. Any interference with the right to privacy must be in accordance with the law and shall be balanced with competing values and objectives of democratic societies. For example, the use by the courts of documents from medical records¹² may be – in certain circumstances – considered as interferences. Therefore, for the development and use of *in silico* technologies, adherence to ECHR is fundamental.

⁶ Council of Europe, Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms (European Convention on Human Rights, as amended) (ECHR, 1950).

⁷ United Nations, Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR, 1948).

⁸ *Panteleyenko v Ukraine* App no 11901/02 (ECHR, 29 June 2006).

⁹ *KH and Others v Slovakia* App no 32881/04 (ECHR, 28 April 2009).

¹⁰ *Reyez Jimenez v Spain* App no 57020/18 (ECHR, 8 March 2022).

¹¹ *Mockute v Lithuania* App no 66490/09 (ECHR, 27 February 2018).

¹² *LL v France* App no 7508/02 (ECHR, 10 February 2006).

The Council of Europe Convention 108

Overview

The Convention for the protection of individuals with regard to automatic processing of personal data (**Convention 108**)¹³ was the first legally binding international instrument in the data protection field. It was opened for signature in 1981 by the Council of Europe. Fifty-one countries are part of the Convention, and all the EU MS have ratified it. The Convention contains general principles and rules, which the CoE Committee of Ministers has further developed through the means of non-binding recommendations. The convention was amended in 2001 with an Additional Protocol introducing provisions on transborder data flows to third countries and requiring the establishment of national data protection supervisory authorities.¹⁴

The convention underwent a **process of modernisation** that resulted in the adoption of Protocol CETS No. 223¹⁵, which was deemed necessary to address the challenges for privacy resulting from new information and communication technologies and strengthen the convention's follow-up mechanisms. The Convention is binding to the states that have ratified it. It is not subject to the judicial supervision of the ECtHR. However, it was taken into account by the Court in several judgments – for example, for determining whether or not there has been interference with the fundamental right to privacy.¹⁶

The Convention aims to protect every individual with regard to the processing of their personal data. It applies to all data processing carried out by the public and private sectors. The Convention lays down **basic principles** for the processing of personal data and seeks at the same time to regulate the transborder flows of personal data.¹⁷ Rules laid down require the fair and lawful **collection and automatic processing of data**. Personal data undergoing processing shall be (a) processed fairly and in a transparent manner; (b) collected for explicit, specified and legitimate purposes; (c) adequate, relevant and not excessive in relation to the purposes for which are processed; (d) accurate and kept up to date; (e) preserved in a form that permits identification of data subjects for no longer than it is necessary for the purposes for which those data are processed.¹⁸

The Convention also contains a prohibition to process **sensitive personal data**¹⁹, if the processing is not complemented by appropriate safeguards enshrined in law. Worth also to mention, the Convention provides for data subjects rights, including the right to information and right to rectification or erasure, as well the right not to be subject to a decision significantly affecting them based solely on automated processing.

Relevance to In Silico World

Personal data in the development or use of *in silico* technologies may be used and that is the reason why Convention 108 is relevant. The states where the partners of ISW are established are signatories of the Convention and therefore the principles laid down by the Convention are relevant, and applicable.

¹³ Council of Europe, Convention for the Protection of Individuals with regard to Automatic Processing of Personal Data, ETS No. 108, 28.01.1981 <<https://www.coe.int/en/web/conventions/full-list/-/conventions/treaty/108>> (Convention 108, as amended in Convention 108+).

¹⁴ Council of Europe, Additional protocol to Convention 108 regarding supervisory authorities and transborder data flows, ETS No. 181, 8.11.2001 <<https://rm.coe.int/1680080626>>.

¹⁵ Council of Europe, Protocol amending the Convention for the Protection of Individuals with regard to Automatic Processing of Personal Data, 10.10.2018 <<https://rm.coe.int/16808ac918>>.

¹⁶ ECtHR, *Z. v. Finland*, No. 22009/93, 25 February 1997.

¹⁷ Convention 108+, chapter II.

¹⁸ Convention 108+, art 5.

¹⁹ Convention 108+, art 6.

The OECD Guidelines on the Protection of Privacy and Transborder Flows of Personal Data

Overview

The Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) Guidelines on Trans-border Data Flows, and the Protection of Privacy (the '**Privacy Guidelines**')²⁰ were adopted on 23 September 1980. They were the first internationally agreed-upon statement of core information privacy principles reflecting the different views and perspectives of countries around the world.

The OECD adopted this set of Guidelines to address concerns about threats to privacy from more intensive use of personal data and the challenges posed by the restrictions on the flow of information to the global economy.²¹ Since then, guidelines have influenced the development of national data protection legislation and model codes within the OECD member countries, and they were recently updated in 2013. The Guidelines apply to personal data, whether in the public or private sectors, which, because of the manner in which they are processed or because of their nature or the context in which they are used, pose a risk to privacy and individual liberties.²²

The Guidelines contain an important **set of basic principles** regarding the processing of personal data. These are the following: collection limitation, data quality, purpose specification, use limitation, security safeguards, openness, individual participation and accountability. The new concepts introduced in 2013 included new aspects concerning national privacy strategies, privacy management programmes and data security breach notification.

Relevance to In Silico World

OECD rules are not binding. However, they represent a significant political commitment on the part of the member countries and a relevant benchmark to consider in implementing privacy and data protection legal requirements. In its principles and requirements may represent and further interpretative support for the application of data protection requirements set by the binding legislation.

The Council of Europe Recommendation on the protection of health-related data

Overview

The increased use of digital technology and the considerable changes in the digital environment in recent years showed the need for **updated guidance for authorities and actors in the healthcare systems**. To provide member States with guidelines on regulating the processing of health-related data to guarantee respect for individuals' rights and fundamental freedoms, the Council of Europe's Committee of Ministers in 2019 adopted its Recommendation on the protection of health-related data.²³ The Recommendation includes a set of guidelines addressed to the 47 Member States of the Council of Europe and should be read in conjunction with the amended version of the Council of Europe Convention 108. This Recommendation is addressed at the 47 Member States of the Council of Europe, calling on transmitting these guidelines to healthcare systems and actors processing health-related data, particularly healthcare professionals and data protection officers.

²⁰ OECD, *OECD Guidelines on the Protection of Privacy and Transborder Flows of Personal Data*, 23 September 1980 <<https://www.oecd.org/sti/ieconomy/oecdguidelinesonthe protectionofprivacyandtransborderflowsofpersonaldata.htm>> (OECD Privacy Guidelines).

²¹ OECD, *The Evolving Privacy Landscape: 30 Years After the OECD Privacy Guidelines*, (OECD Digital Economy Papers, No. 176, OECD Publishing, Paris) <<http://dx.doi.org/10.1787/5kgf09z90c31-en>> accessed 23 March 2022.

²² OECD, Privacy Guidelines – §2 Scope of the Guidelines.

²³ Council of Europe, Recommendation on the protection of health-related data – Recommendation CM/Rec(2019)2 (2019).

The Recommendation applies to the **processing of personal data relating to health in the public and private sectors**.²⁴ It includes provisions concerning legal conditions for the processing of health-related data. Some of the principles require that data must be processed in a transparent, lawful and fair manner, to be collected for explicit, specific and legitimate purposes, and must not be processed in a way that is incompatible with these purposes. Further processing for scientific purposes is not regarded as incompatible with the initial purposes, where appropriate guarantees enable rights and fundamental freedoms to be respected. The processing of data should be carried out on the basis of the consent of the data subject, or another legitimate basis, such as preventive medical or diagnostic purposes, reasons of public health, safeguarding the vital interests of the data subject, reasons of public interests.

The Recommendation contains provisions on data subjects' rights, concerning transparency of processing, information of the data subject, even in the case where an **individual's wish is not to be informed of a diagnosis or prognosis**. In that case, the Recommendation suggests that this wish should be complied with, except where this constitutes a serious risk for the health of others.²⁵ Further provisions concern access to data, rectification, erasure, objection to processing, data portability and also security of processing and interoperability. Chapter V of the Recommendation on scientific research requires the **processing of health-related data for the purposes of scientific research** shall be subject to appropriate safeguards provided for by law, carried out with a legitimate aim and be in compliance with the rights and fundamental freedoms of the data subject. When scientific research purposes allow, data should be anonymised. Where a data subject withdraws from a scientific research project, their health-related data processed in the context of that research should be destroyed or anonymised in a manner that does not compromise the scientific validity of the research, and the data subject should be informed accordingly.

Relevance to In Silico World

The conduction of the In Silico World project entails several aspects concerning the use of health-related data for scientific research. The provisions offered by the Recommendation are therefore relevant to In Silico World.²⁶ Adherence to this Recommendation will need to be evaluated carefully, in light of the other existing legislation and recommendations at the EU and national level.

The Treaty on the European Union and the on the Functioning of the European Union

Overview

The **Treaty on the European Union (TEU)**²⁷ and the **Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union (TFEU)**²⁸ lay down the foundations of EU primary law together with the Charter. They establish the objectives of the European Union, the rules for EU institutions, and the relationships between the EU and its Member States. Every action taken by the EU is founded on treaties. The treaties are binding agreements negotiated and agreed upon by all EU Member States, and their parliaments ratify them.

Several provisions of the treaties are relevant. Regarding the **TFEU, Article 16** states that everyone has the **right to protect personal data**. The article is of particular importance because it establishes the competence of the European Parliament and the Council to legislate on the matter of data protection through the ordinary procedure – whilst, before, data protection rules were based on the internal market legal basis and

²⁴ CM/Rec(2019)2, §2.

²⁵ CM/Rec(2019)2, §11.7

²⁶ It is worth to note that the legal framework concerning consent for health-related data and research purposes is not uniform. See Kamenjašević E, 'Health data for scientific research under the CoE Recommendation and the GDPR – Part II' (*KU Leuven CiTiP Blog*, 14 May 2019) <<https://www.law.kuleuven.be/citip/blog/health-data-for-scientific-research-under-the-coe-recommendation-and-the-gdpr-part-ii/>> accessed 23 March 2022.

²⁷ Consolidated Version of the Treaty on European Union [2008] OJ C115/13 (TEU).

²⁸ Consolidated version of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union [2007] OJ C 115/47 (TFEU).

approximation of laws. The same article restates that compliance with data protection rules must be subject to the control of independent supervisory authorities.

Relevance to In Silico World

From a pragmatic point of view, both provisions of the treaties and the Charter are of limited practical relevance since many of the activities pursued by the Consortium are covered by secondary and more specific legislation. However, in case practical implementation may disclose legal uncertainties, guidance and interpretation of secondary law will have to be in accordance with the sources provided by primary EU law and international treaties and conventions.

Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union (Charter)

Overview

The **Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union** (CFREU)²⁹ is an act of primary legislation of the EU containing a list of human rights recognised by the European Union. The Charter entered into force in 2009. The European Communities' original treaties did not include any reference to human rights and their protection since the European Economic Community was initially founded to function as a regional organisation to foster economic integration and the establishment of a common market.

The Charter was born in 2000 only as a political document and became legally binding in 2009 as EU primary law when the Lisbon Treaty came into force on 1 December 2009. All 27 EU Member States shall guarantee the fundamental rights enshrined by the Charter when implementing European Union Law.

The Charter brings together all the personal, civic, political, economic and social rights enjoyed by people within the EU in a single text. It covers all the rights found in the ECJ case law, the rights and freedoms enshrined in the ECHR, and the other rights and principles resulting from the common constitutional traditions of EU countries and other international instruments.

The Charter contains rights and freedoms under six titles: dignity, freedoms, equality, solidarity, citizen's rights, and justice. It guarantees **the respect for private and family life** (Article 7), unitedly with the **right to protection of personal data** (Article 8). Article 7, notably, establishes that everyone has the right to respect for their private and family life, home and communications. Article 8 establishes that everyone has the right to the protection of personal data. Data should be processed fairly for specified purposes and on the basis of consent or some other legitimate basis laid down by law. An independent supervisory authority should control the compliance with data protection legislative provisions. Article 21 of the Charter prohibits any discrimination based on any ground such as sex, race colour, ethnic or social origin, genetic features, language, religion or belief, political or any other opinion, membership of a national minority, property, birth, disability, age or sexual orientation. Article 23 contains the principle of equality between men and women, and Article 26 promotes the integration of persons with disabilities. Article 35 foresees that everyone has the right of access to preventive health care and the right to benefit from medical treatment.

Article 52(1) of the Charter outlines the scope of the fundamental rights. According to it, any limitation on the exercise of the rights and freedoms recognised by the Charter must be provided by law and **respect the essence of those fundamental rights** and freedoms. Furthermore, these must be, subject to the principle of proportionality, necessary and shall genuinely meet the objectives of general interest recognised by the Union or the need to protect the rights and freedoms of others.

²⁹ Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union [2007] OJ C303/1 (CFREU).

Relevance to the ISW project

ISW solutions may entail the processing of personal data of individuals. Therefore, the design and deployment of ISW solutions shall take into consideration the fundamental rights to privacy and data protection set by the Charter.

The General Data Protection Legislation (GDPR)

Overview

Regulation 2016/679, also known as **General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)**³⁰, is the core piece of EU secondary legislation which sets rules on the protection of personal data in the EU. It entered into force on 25 May 2018, and it **replaced Directive 95/46/EC** (also known as Data Protection Directive, or DPD)³¹. The Regulation was adopted after a long process of modernisation of the legal framework, rendered necessary in order to align with recent technology developments on the one hand, and the exigence of creating a common set of rules for the EU Member States that could be of direct application. In fact, the rules previously established by DPD were not directly applicable as they had to be transposed into national laws by every Member State. Even if there was a common legal canvas for the application of data protection requirements, in fact, there was a heterogeneous situation in the application of data protection across the Member States.

After May 2018, the Regulation became directly applicable in the EU, meaning that the EU Member States shall abide by it. Following the path of the DPD, the GDPR has updated the EU data protection legal framework by preserving the core principles while introducing new legal requirements. Some rules of the GDPR still leave open some **margin of manoeuvre** from the Member States in certain circumstances and for specific matters – including **health law**.

Context and scope

The GDPR lays down rules relating to the protection of **natural persons** with regard to the processing of personal data and rules relating to the free movement of personal data. It applies to the processing of personal data wholly or partly by automated means and to the processing other than automated means of personal data which form part of a filing system or are intended to form part of a filing system. The regulation does not apply to the processing of personal data by a natural person in the course of a purely personal or household activity or by competent authorities for the purposes of the prevention, investigation, detection or prosecution of criminal offences or the execution of criminal penalties, including the safeguarding against and the prevention of threats to public security.

In line with the preceding DPD, the GDPR foresees rules for the processing of personal data, starting from the **principles** relating to the processing of personal data. **Lawfulness, fairness and transparency** require to be processed lawfully, fairly and in a transparent manner in relation to the data subject.³² The **purpose limitation** implies that data shall be collected for specified, explicit and legitimate purposes and not further processed in a manner that is incompatible with those purposes.³³ **Data minimisation** foresees that data shall be adequate, relevant and limited to what is necessary for relation to the purposes for which they are processed.³⁴ Furthermore, data shall be accurate and, where necessary, kept up to date (**accuracy**).³⁵ Also, data shall be kept in a form which permits identification of data subjects for no longer than is necessary for the purposes

³⁰ Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation) [2016] OJ L119/1 (GDPR).

³¹ Directive 95/46/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 24 October 1995 on the protection of individuals with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data [1995] OJ L281/31.

³² GDPR, art 5(1)(a).

³³ GDPR, art 5(1)(b).

³⁴ GDPR, art 5(1)(c).

³⁵ GDPR, art 5(1)(d).

for which the personal data are processed (**storage limitation**).³⁶ Finally, as per the principle of **integrity and confidentiality and accountability**, data shall be processed in a manner that ensures appropriate security of the personal data and using appropriate technical or organisational measures.³⁷ As an overarching principle, **accountability** requires the controller to be responsible for and be able to demonstrate compliance with the principles above enlisted.³⁸

The GDPR establishes the underlying **lawfulness grounds** for the processing of personal data³⁹ and rules on **consent**.⁴⁰ Processing of special categories of personal data is prohibited except in some specific circumstances. The GDPR contains further rules on **data subjects' rights**, which include the right of access, the right to rectification, the right to erasure, the right to restrict processing, the right to data portability, the right to object and the right not to be subject to a decision based solely on automated processing⁴¹

The GDPR also foresees **security requirements** for the processing of personal data⁴² – which include data breach notification⁴³ and the execution of Data Protection Impact Assessments in certain circumstances⁴⁴ – the adherence to codes of conduct and certification⁴⁵, and third country personal data transfers⁴⁶.

Relevance to the ISW project

The activities carried out in ISW may involve the processing of personal data. The **GDPR** shall be regarded as a **core regulation establishing baseline requirements for the protection of individuals' personal data**. To offer support in the alignment with it, the forthcoming deliverable of WP9 will include further specifications of the GDPR's legal requirements, as applied to *in silico* technologies.

Other relevant documentation and guidance on data protection

The European Data Protection Board / Article 29 Working Party

The consistent application of data protection rules throughout the EU is facilitated by the **European Data Protection Board (EDPB)**. The EDPB is an independent European body that was established by the GDPR. Before that, the consistent application of data protection rules was also possible thanks to the guidance provided by the Article 29 Working Party (WP29), pursuant to Article 29 of the DPD.

Throughout the years of application of the DPD and the GDPR, these two EU bodies have provided a number of guidance documents in the form of opinions, recommendations and best practices that, although not binding, became increasingly relevant for all actors in the data protection law field.

Amongst the many documents, the most pertinent guidance for *in silico* technologies is the following:

- EDPB Guidelines 1/2022 on data subject rights – Right of access⁴⁷
- EDPB Guidelines 07/2020 on the concepts of controller and processor in the GDPR⁴⁸
- EDPB Guidelines 4/2019 on Article 25 Data Protection by Design and by Default⁴⁹

³⁶ GDPR, art 5(1)(e).

³⁷ GDPR, art 5(1)(f).

³⁸ GDPR, art 5(2).

³⁹ GDPR, art 6.

⁴⁰ GDPR, art 7.

⁴¹ GDPR, ch III.

⁴² GDPR, art 32.

⁴³ GDPR, arts 33-34.

⁴⁴ GDPR, art 35 and see *infra* about related guidelines by WP29.

⁴⁵ GDPR, arts 40-42.

⁴⁶ GDPR, ch V.

⁴⁷ European Data Protection Board, 'Guidelines 01/2022 on data subject rights - Right of access' (2022).

⁴⁸ European Data Protection Board, 'Guidelines 07/2020 on the concepts of controller and processor in the GDPR' (2020).

⁴⁹ European Data Protection Board, 'Guidelines 4/2019 on Article 25 Data Protection by Design and by Default' (2019).

- EDPB Guidelines 05/2020 on consent under Regulation 2016/679⁵⁰
- EDPB Guidelines 03/2020 on the processing of data concerning health for the purpose of scientific research in the context of the COVID-19 outbreak⁵¹
- WP29 Guidelines on transparency under Regulation 2016/679⁵²
- WP29 Guidelines on Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) and determining whether processing is "likely to result in a high risk" for the purposes of Regulation 2016/679⁵³
- WP29 Guidelines on Automated individual decision-making and Profiling for the purposes of Regulation 2016/679⁵⁴

Although issued before the entering into application of the GDPR, the following guidance by WP29 is also relevant. Their contents, even if referred to the former DPD, offer argumentations that may be worth to be interpreted having regard to the GDPR.

- WP29 Opinion 05/2014 on Anonymisation Techniques⁵⁵
- WP29 Opinion 06/2013 on open data and public sector information ('PSI') re-use⁵⁶
- WP29 Opinion 03/2013 on purpose limitation⁵⁷
- WP29 Opinion 4/2007 on the concept of personal data⁵⁸
- WP29 Opinion 7/2003 on the re-use of public sector information and the protection of personal data— Striking the balance⁵⁹

The European Data Protection Supervisor

The **European Data Protection Supervisor** (EDPS) is an independent supervisory authority whose primary objective is to monitor that European institutions and bodies respect the right to privacy and data protection. As an additional duty, the EDPS has a consultative role and advises the European Commission, the European Parliament and the Council of the European union on data protection issues in a range of policy areas. Therefore, the opinions provided by the EDPS become relevant as an interpretative means of the existing laws or proposed legislation in the EU. In certain cases, these opinion clarify the meaning of certain concepts (such as 'scientific research' and 'privacy by design' as it can be noted from the below documents.

- EDPS A Preliminary Opinion on data protection and scientific research⁶⁰
- EDPS Opinion on the proposal for a recast of the Public Sector Information (PSI) re-use Directive⁶¹
- EDPS Preliminary Opinion on privacy by design⁶²

⁵⁰ European Data Protection Board, 'Guidelines 05/2020 on consent under Regulation 2016/679' (2020).

⁵¹ European Data Protection Board, 'Guidelines 03/2020 on the processing of data concerning health for the purpose of scientific research in the context of the COVID-19 outbreak' (2020).

⁵² Article 29 Working Party, 'Guidelines on transparency under Regulation 2016/679' (2017, as last revised in April 2018). The Guidelines were endorsed by the EDPB during its first plenary meeting on 28 May 2018.

⁵³ Article 29 Working Party, 'Guidelines on Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) and determining whether processing is "likely to result in a high risk" for the purposes of Regulation 2016/679' (2017). The Guidelines were endorsed by the EDPB during its first plenary meeting on 28 May 2018.

⁵⁴ Article 29 Working Party, 'WP29 Guidelines on Automated individual decision-making and Profiling for the purposes of Regulation 2016/679' (2017). The Guidelines were endorsed by the EDPB during its first plenary meeting on 28 May 2018.

⁵⁵ Article 29 Working Party, 'Opinion 05/2014 on Anonymisation Techniques' (2014).

⁵⁶ Article 29 Working Party, 'Opinion 06/2013 on open data and public sector information ('PSI') reuse' (2013).

⁵⁷ Article 29 Working Party, 'Opinion 03/2013 on purpose limitation' (2013).

⁵⁸ Article 29 Working Party, 'Opinion 4/2007 on the concept of personal data' (2007).

⁵⁹ Article 29 Working Party, 'Opinion 7/2003 on the re-use of public sector information and the protection of personal data - Striking the balance -' (2003).

⁶⁰ European Data Protection Supervisor, 'A Preliminary Opinion on data protection and scientific research' (2020).

⁶¹ European Data Protection Supervisor, 'Opinion on the proposal for a recast of the Public Sector Information (PSI) re-use Directive' (2018).

⁶² European Data Protection Supervisor, 'Preliminary Opinion on privacy by design' (2018).

- EDPS Mobile Health⁶³
- EDPS Opinion of the European Data Protection Supervisor on the Commission proposals for a Regulation on medical devices, and amending Directive 2001/83/EC, Regulation (EC) No 178/2002 and Regulation (EC) No 1223/2009 and a Regulation on in vitro diagnostic medical devices (2013)⁶⁴
- EDPS Opinion of the European Data Protection Supervisor on the Communication from the Commission on 'eHealth Action Plan 2012-2020—Innovative healthcare for the 21st century'⁶⁵
- EDPS Opinion of the European Data Protection Supervisor on the Commission proposal for a Regulation on clinical trials on medicinal products for human use, and repealing Directive 2001/20/EC⁶⁶

3. Data Governance

Introduction

The growing interest in data markets and commodification of data has led the European legislator to consider the data economy as a new regulatory domain to regulate **data as an economic asset**. In the past years, the Commission issued a set of policy documentation, followed by legislative proposals and other initiatives that are related to the data economy and its regulation. This section proposes a brief illustration of the current regulatory panorama on data governance. As the framework is currently evolving, the illustration of related policy-making initiatives is essential in order to grasp the most recent legislative proposals set at the EU level. The outline, therefore will start from these and will then present the existing legislation and the recently proposed pieces of it.

Policy-making initiatives

Towards a Common European Data Space (2018)

One of the first relevant policy documentation for the data governance framework dates back to 2018 when the European Commission issued the 'Towards a common European data space' Communication.⁶⁷ Starting from the acknowledgement that data driven-innovation should be a key driver for growth and the European market, the Commission set the objective to propose a package of measures for establishing a **common data space in the EU**. In the Commission's vision, a common data space should be 'a seamless digital area with the scale that will enable the development of new products and services based on data'.⁶⁸

To do so, the Commission identified several areas to work on. For instance, the Commission set the intention to review the Directive on the re-use of public sector information (PSI Directive),⁶⁹ to issue new guidance on private-sector data sharing, and to update the recommendation on access and preservation of scientific

⁶³ European Data Protection Supervisor 'Opinion on Mobile Health - Reconciling technological innovation with data protection' (2015).

⁶⁴ European Data Protection Supervisor 'Opinion on the Commission proposals for a Regulation on medical devices, and amending Directive 2001/83/EC, Regulation (EC) No 178/2002 and Regulation (EC) No 1223/2009 and a Regulation on in vitro diagnostic medical devices' (2013).

⁶⁵ European Data Protection Supervisor, 'EDPS Opinion of the European Data Protection Supervisor on the Communication from the Commission on 'eHealth Action Plan 2012-2020—Innovative healthcare for the 21st century' (2013).

⁶⁶ European Data Protection Supervisor, 'Opinion of the European Data Protection Supervisor on the Commission proposal for a Regulation on clinical trials on medicinal products for human use, and repealing Directive 2001/20/EC' (2012).

⁶⁷ Commission, 'Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of Regions "Towards a common European data space" COM(2018) 232 final (Towards a common European data space).

⁶⁸ *ibid*, 1.

⁶⁹ Directive 2013/37/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 26 June 2013 amending Directive 2003/98/EC on the re-use of public sector information Text with EEA relevance [2013] OJ L175/1 (PSI Directive).

information. The PSI review resulted in the Open Data Directive⁷⁰ (see *infra*), while further work on data access and sharing may be envisaged in the recent Data Governance Act⁷¹ and Data Act proposal⁷² (*infra*).

Concerning specifically healthcare, the Commission identified **three key areas** to stimulate innovation in healthcare solutions:

- (1) citizens' secure access to and sharing of health data;
- (2) better data to promote research, disease prevention and personalised healthcare;
- (3) digital tools for citizen empowerment and person-centred care.⁷³

After enunciating these, the Commission further worked on possible initiatives related to these three key areas in subsequent policy documentation.⁷⁴

European Strategy for Data (2020)

The 2018 'Towards a common European data space Communication' was followed by the **European Strategy for Data** in 2020,⁷⁵ where the European Commission outlined its vision to establish rules and enforcement mechanisms to ensure that data can flow within the EU and across sectors. In this document, the Commission outlines the need to set fair, practical, and clear rules for access and use of data and have trustworthy data governance mechanisms in place.⁷⁶ In the Commission's opinion, some issues hold back the achievements data access, re-use and sharing. Among the many, the first is data (un)availability. There would not enough **data available for innovative re-use, including the development of artificial intelligence**. The problem would insist at the following levels:

- use of public sector information by business (*government-to-business – G2B – data sharing*)
- sharing and use of privately-held data by other companies (*business-to-business – B2B – data sharing*)
- use of privately-held data by government authorities (*business-to-government – B2G – data sharing*);
- sharing of data between public authorities.

Other problems include data governance, imbalances in market power, data interoperability and quality, data infrastructures and technologies, cybersecurity. In order to overcome these, the Commission's strategy includes the **establishment of a cross-sectoral governance framework for data access and use through common European data spaces**. Further, the Commission set the intention to explore the need for legislative action on issues concerning actors in a 'data-agile' economy, such as the **European Data Act**.⁷⁷ This action was announced to be complemented with the promotion of **common 'European data spaces'** in strategic

⁷⁰ Directive (EU) 2019/1024 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 June 2019 on open data and the re-use of public sector information [2019] OJ 172/56 (Open Data Directive).

⁷¹ Commission, 'Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on European Data Governance (Data Governance Act)' COM(2020) 767 final (hereinafter, Data Governance Act or DGA).

⁷² Commission, 'Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on harmonised rules on fair access to and use of data (Data Act)' COM(2022) 68 final (Data Act proposal).

⁷³ Towards a common European data space, 3. These were based on remarks of Commission, 'Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee of the Regions of the Mid-Term Review on the implementation of the Digital Single Market Strategy A Connected Digital Single Market for All' COM(2017) 0228 final.

⁷⁴ See *infra*, section 'Enabling the digital transformation of health and care in the Digital Single Market (2018)'.

⁷⁵ Commission, 'Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions. A European Strategy for Data' COM (2020) 66 final (European Strategy for Data).

⁷⁶ *ibid*, 5.

⁷⁷ *ibid*, 13.

economic sectors and domains of public interest.⁷⁸ Healthcare is included in the strategic economic sectors as part of the **Common European health data space**.

Enabling the digital transformation of health and care in the Digital Single Market (2018)

The 2018 Commission's Communication on 'enabling the digital transformation of health and care in the Digital Single Market'⁷⁹ concerns healthcare data notably. The document served the function, among others, to outline the actions to undertake having regard to the three key areas to stimulate innovation in healthcare identified in the 2018 Communication Towards a European Data space (i.e. citizens' secure access to and sharing of health data; better data to promote research, disease prevention and personalised healthcare; digital tools for citizen empowerment and person-centred care).

For the first area, 'Citizen's access to and sharing of health data', the Commission announced its review on Implementing Decision 2011/890 on the **eHealth network**, which lately happened in 2019.⁸⁰ Moreover, the Commission communicated the forthcoming adoption of a 'Recommendation on **technical specifications for a European electronic health record**', which was published later in 2019.⁸¹

For the second key area 'Better data to promote research, disease prevention and personalised healthcare', the Commission set out its intention to step up coordination between authorities across the EU to implement the secure exchange of **genomic and other health data** to advance research and personalised medicine. The coordination of the EU states should lead to the integration of molecular profiling, diagnostic imaging, lifestyle, microbiological genomics and environmental data as well as links to electronic health records.⁸² Launching this kind of initiative could 'also build on "**digital patient**" **predictive approaches based on computer modelling, simulations and artificial intelligence**'⁸³ and it could 'lay down the foundation for the development of a reference map (atlas) of all human cells, with a view to analyse human tissues and organs by state-of-the-art methodologies, and to compare and understand changes during disease'.⁸⁴

Concerning the third area, 'digital tools for citizen empowerment and for person-centred care', the Commission identified several factors to improve the effectiveness, accessibility and resilience of health systems, including the configuration of new care models, use of health technology assessment, the utilisation of digital solutions, the involvement of multi-disciplinary care teams with new or redesigned roles for care professionals.⁸⁵ Financial investments and other stakeholder coordination activities were programmed concerning this area. Also, and more relevantly on **health technology assessment**, the EU legislator amended

⁷⁸ *ibid*, 21.

⁷⁹ Commission, 'Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions Empty on enabling the digital transformation of health and care in the Digital Single Market; empowering citizens and building a healthier society' COM(2018) 233 (Communication on digital transformation of health and care).

⁸⁰ Commission, 'Commission Implementing Decision 2019/1765 of 22 October 2019 providing the rules for the establishment, the management and the functioning of the network of national authorities responsible for eHealth, and repealing Implementing Decision 2011/980/EU [2019] OJ L270/83.

⁸¹ Commission, 'Commission Recommendation (EU) 2019/243 of 6 February 2019 on a European Electronic Health Record exchange format' [2019] L39/18.

⁸² Commission, Communication on digital transformation of health and care, 8.

⁸³ *ibid*, emphasis added.

⁸⁴ *ibid*.

⁸⁵ *ibid*, 11.

the existing Directive 2011/24/EU⁸⁶ with Regulation 2021/2282⁸⁷, which entered into force on January 11, 2022 and will be applicable as of January 12, 2025.

Commission Staff working document on Common European Data Spaces (2022)

On 23 February 2022, the European Commission published – along with the Data Act proposal – a Working Document on Common European Data Spaces⁸⁸. The document provided an overview of the common European Data Spaces currently developed in various sectors or domains in response to the European strategy for data. The document included the state of play of the announced common European data spaces, including the health data space.⁸⁹

The Working Document shared some details about the Commission's legislative proposal for a European Health Data Space (EHDS), which was released in May 2022.⁹⁰

According to the Communication, the EHDS proposal shall complement the horizontal data framework, such as the Data Governance Act, with more sectorial measures in the area of health, having regard to three objectives:

- **Primary use of health data:** promoting the access, sharing and use of health data for healthcare delivery purposes, as well as control by individuals over their health data;
- **Secondary use of health data:** removing barriers to access and reuse of health data for research, innovation, public health policy making and regulatory activities, 'in a privacy preserving, secure, timely, transparent and trustful way, with an appropriate institutional governance'⁹¹;
- **Single market:** fostering a single market for digital health services and products, included those based on AI.

Legal Framework

The Free Flow of Non Personal Data Regulation

Overview

Regulation 2018/1807 on a framework for the free flow of non-personal data (Free Flow of Non-Personal Data Regulation or FFPDR)⁹² is an EU piece of secondary legislation adopted in 2018 and became applicable as of 28 May 2019. With this Regulation, the EU aims to promote the 'free flow' of data in Europe to allow **companies and public administrations to store and process non-personal data without restrictions**. The EU legislator felt the necessity to introduce this regulation as they noticed the effective and efficient functioning of data processing and development of the data economy in the Union were hampered by two types of obstacles to data mobility and the internal market: data localisation requirements put in place by Member State's authorities and vendor lock-in practices in the private sectors.

⁸⁶ Directive 2011/24/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 9 March 2011 on the application of patients' rights in cross-border healthcare [2011] OJ L88/45.

⁸⁷ Regulation (EU) 2021/2282 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 15 December 2021 on health technology assessment and amending Directive 2011/24/EU [2021] OJ L458/1 (HTAR).

⁸⁸ Commission, 'Commission Staff Working Document on Common European Data Spaces' SWD(2022) 45 final (Working Document on CEDS).

⁸⁹ *ibid*, 20.

⁹⁰ *ibid*.

⁹¹ *ibid*.

⁹² Regulation (EU) 2018/1807 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 November 2018 on a framework for the free flow of non-personal data in the European Union [2018] OJ L303/59 (FFPDR).

Context and scope

The FFPDR aims to ensure the free flow of data other than personal data within the Union by laying down rules relating to data localisation requirements, the availability of data to competent authorities and the porting of data for professional users. It applies to the processing of electronic data other than personal data in the Union provided as a service to users in the EU or carried out by natural or legal persons in the EU. The Regulation applies without prejudice to the provisions set by the GDPR. Three main aspects are worth noting.

First, the Regulation **prohibits** the Member States from setting **data localisation requirements** – unless they are justified on the grounds of public security, in compliance with the principle of proportionality. Second, the regulation aims at **ensuring data availability for regulatory control**. Third, it encourages the development of a **code of conduct for cloud services to facilitate data portability**.

Relevance to In Silico World

The FFPDR basically contains requirements that are addressed to the EU's the Member States. However, the Regulation is a core element in framing the concept of 'personal data' and 'non-personal' data in the context of the privacy and data protection legal framework. Therefore, while it is of limited practical utility in terms of requirements implementation, it represents a useful interpretative tool for concepts in data protection and data governance regulation.

Open Data Directive

Overview

The Directive on open data and the re-use of public sector information (known as '**Open Data Directive**' (ODD)) establishes a set of minimum rules governing the re-use and the practical arrangements for facilitating the re-use of data.⁹³ It entered into force on 16 July 2019 and **replaced the former applicable Public Sector Information (PSI) Directive**⁹⁴. The EU Member States had to transpose the Directive by 16 July 2021.

The Directive aims to bring the legislation up to date with the advances in digital technologies and to address the barriers to the re-use of publicly funded information across the EU (European Commission).⁹⁵ The recast had the objective to increase the availability of data, reduce market entry barriers by limiting the exceptions that allow public bodies to charge for the re-use of their data, increase the availability of data by bringing new types of public and publicly funded data into the scope of the Directive.

Context and scope

The Directive introduces an **obligation for public bodies to publish available data unless access is restricted or excluded**. The main new aspects are threefold. First, they concern charging: the new main principle of the directive is that the re-use of public information shall be **free of charge**, unless in certain cases.⁹⁶ The re-use shall follow the principle of 'open by default' and be compatible with the FAIR principles.⁹⁷ Second, when charges for the re-use of documents apply, applicable conditions and amount of those charges shall be pre-

⁹³ By 're-use of data' the Directive means 'the use for purposes other than the initial purpose within the public task for which the documents or the information were produced, apply to public authorities when they provide information for re-use' (Article 2(11) ODD).

⁹⁴ Directive 2003/98/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 November 2003 on the re-use of public sector information [2003] OJ 345/90.

⁹⁵ Amongst the barriers, the EU legislator found "that several public sector bodies continue to charge well above what is needed to cover reproduction and dissemination costs for the re-use of public sector data, resulting in a market barrier for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs)" (European Commission, n.d.). Another example: Public data holders enter into arrangements with the private sector to derive extra value from their data, creating the risk of lock-in of public sector data, benefiting large companies and thereby limiting the number of potential re-users of the data in question (id.).

⁹⁶ ODD, art 6(1).

⁹⁷ ODD, art 6(1).

established and published (**transparency**).⁹⁸ Public sector bodies shall ensure that applicants for re-use of documents are informed of available means of redress relating to decisions or practices affecting them. Third, the conditions for the re-use of documents shall be non-discriminatory for comparable categories of re-use, including for cross-border re-use.⁹⁹

As further requirements, Member States shall support the availability of research data¹⁰⁰ by adopting national policies and relevant actions aiming at making publicly funded research data openly available (open access policies). Also, Member States must ensure that public sector bodies will make dynamic data available for re-use immediately after collection.¹⁰¹ **High-value datasets** (which are 'documents whose re-use is associated with important benefits for society, the environment and the economy')¹⁰² will be governed by a separate set of rules. The European Commission has mandate to decide on a list of them through implementing acts.¹⁰³

Finally, when it comes to concerns relating to intellectual property rights, privacy and personal data protection and confidentiality, security and legitimate commercial interests, the principle of 'as open as possible as closed as necessary' shall be taken into account.¹⁰⁴

The Data Governance Act

Overview

The **Data Governance Act** (DGA) is a legislative proposal put forward by the European Commission on November 25, 2020. The DGA is one of the deliverables included in the EC's 2020 European Strategy for Data. Its objective is to foster the availability of data for use in the economy and society while promising to keep companies and individuals who generate the data in their control. As it covers the reuse of data, the DGA is expected to **complement the Open Data Directive**. According to its Explanatory Memorandum, the DGA will address the following situations: making public sector data available for re-use in situations where such data is subject to rights of others; sharing data amongst businesses against remuneration in any form; allowing personal data to be used with the help of a 'personal data sharing intermediary' designed to help individuals exercise their rights under the GDPR; allowing data use on altruistic grounds.

Context and scope

The DGA proposal introduces a mechanism **for re-using certain categories of protected public sector data**, conditional on the respect of the rights of others (notably, on grounds of protection of personal data, intellectual property rights and commercial confidentiality).¹⁰⁵ Within this new ecosystem, new actors are envisaged, such as defined entities that provide various types of intermediation services ('data sharing providers'). Notably, data sharing providers would have a series of requirements to comply with and a **notification regime**.¹⁰⁶ Also, the proposal introduces the concept of '**data altruism**', i.e. 'data voluntarily made available by individuals or companies for the common good'.¹⁰⁷ An organisation wishing to engage in data altruism may register as a 'Data Altruism Organisation recognised in the EU'.¹⁰⁸ Also, a common EU data

⁹⁸ ODD, art 7.

⁹⁹ ODD, art 11.

¹⁰⁰ By 'research data' the ODD means 'documents in a digital form, other than scientific publications, which are collected or produced in the course of scientific research activities and are used as evidence in the research process, or are commonly accepted in the research community as necessary to validate research findings and results' (Article 2(9) ODD).

¹⁰¹ ODD, art 5(5).

¹⁰² ODD, art 2(10).

¹⁰³ ODD, art 13.

¹⁰⁴ ODD, art 10(1).

¹⁰⁵ DGA, ch II.

¹⁰⁶ DGA, ch III.

¹⁰⁷ DGA, ch IV.

¹⁰⁸ *ibid.*

altruism consent form would be developed to lower the cost of collecting consent and facilitate data portability.

Relevance to In Silico World

The DGA and, more broadly, the initiatives related to the European Data Space are foreseen to target the healthcare sector through the promotion of an EU Health Data Space and by facilitating mechanisms to allow data sharing and their re-use. As such, the forthcoming requirements foreseen by the DGA, unitedly with the others possibly included in the Data Act and Health Data Space initiative, may be relevant for the *In silico* technologies.

The Data Act proposal

Overview

On 23 February 2022, the European Commission published its Proposal for a Regulation on harmonised rules on fair access to and use of data (also named **Data Act**)¹⁰⁹. Following the Data Governance Act, the Data Act proposal represents the second main legislative initiative stemming from the European Strategy for data, issued in February 2020. While the DGA creates the processes and structures to facilitate data sharing by companies, individuals, and the public sector, the **Data Act sets rules about ‘who can create value from data and under which conditions’**.¹¹⁰ The Data Act is a horizontal proposal, which means that it envisages basic rules for all sectors for the use of data. As its Explanatory Memorandum explicates, the proposal in principle leaves room for vertical legislation to set more detailed rules for the achievement of sector-specific regulatory objectives,¹¹¹ including the healthcare sector. Finally, it is worth noting that the proposal contains several exceptions for small and micro-enterprises.¹¹²

Context and scope

The proposal for the Data Act establishes a set of measures to promote fairer access and sharing of personal data. As Article 1 outlines, the proposal pursues this objective by laying down harmonised rules on making available data: (a) generated by the use of a product or related service, by data holders to data recipients; (b) by data holders to data recipients (following a legal obligation); (c) by data holders to public sector bodies or Union institutions, agencies or bodies, where there is an exceptional need, for the performance of a task carried out in the public interest.¹¹³

The proposal is outlined as follows. Chapter II (*business to consumer and business to business data sharing*) proposes measures to allow **users of connected devices to gain access to data** generated by them. Manufacturers and designers must design the products to make the **data ‘by default, easily, securely directly accessible to the user’** (Article 3).¹¹⁴ Manufacturers shall be transparent on what data will be accessible and how to access them. Chapter III contains rules regulating how data holders must fulfil their obligations to make data available. Chapter IV includes rules to **prevent** abuse of contractual imbalances in data sharing contracts.

¹⁰⁹ Commission, ‘Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on harmonised rules on fair access to and use of data (Data Act)’ COM(2022) 68 final (Data Act proposal).

¹¹⁰ Commission, ‘Data Act: Commission proposes measures for a fair and innovative data economy’ (*European Commission*, 23 February 2022) <https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/ip_22_1113> accessed 4 March 2022.

¹¹¹ Data Act proposal, Explanatory Memorandum, 5. For a brief outline of the Data Act proposal application to eHealth apps and medical devices, see Biasin E, ‘The Data Act will concern eHealth apps and Medical Devices’ (*KU Leven CiTiP Blog*, 19 May 2022) <<https://www.law.kuleuven.be/citip/blog/the-data-act-will-concern-ehealth-apps-and-medical-devices/>> accessed 24 May 2022.

¹¹² See Commission, ‘Commission Recommendation of 6 May 2003 concerning the definition of micro, small and medium-sized enterprises’ [2003] OJ L124/26, Annex, art 2.

¹¹³ *ibid*, art 1(1).

¹¹⁴ *ibid*, art 3.

They target to **rebalance SME negotiation powers** by shifting imbalances from unfair contractual terms imposed by a party with a significantly stronger bargaining position.

Chapter V sets measures for **public sector bodies to access and use data** held by the private sector for exceptional circumstances, where there is an **exceptional need** for the data requested.¹¹⁵ This would be the case of public health emergencies, major natural or human-induced disasters.¹¹⁶ In case of a public emergency, data holders should **make data available free of charge**.¹¹⁷ Data shall be shared with individuals or organisations in view of carrying out scientific research or analytics compatible with the purpose for which the data was requested – or to national statistical institutes and Eurostat for the compilation of official statistics.¹¹⁸ Individuals or organisations receiving the data shall act on a **not-for-profit basis** or in the context of a **public-interest mission** recognised by the law of the EU or of a Member State.¹¹⁹ In the other cases of exceptional need¹²⁰ (beyond the latter research hypothesis and including preventing or assisting the recovery from a public emergency), the data holder making the data available should be entitled to **compensation** that includes costs related to making the relevant data available plus a reasonable margin. To ensure that the right to request data is not abused and that the public sector remains accountable for its use, the requests for data would need to be proportionate, clearly indicate the purpose to be achieved, and respect the interests of the enterprise making the data available. Competent authorities should ensure the transparency and public availability of all requests.

Chapter VI establishes rules for customers to switch between different **cloud-data processing services** providers effectively. The chapter imposes minimum regulatory requirements of contractual, commercial and technical nature for providers of cloud, edge and other data processing services. Chapter VII includes rules about the unlawful third party access to non-personal data held in the Union by data processing services offered on the Union market and puts in place safeguards against **unlawful data transfers**. Chapter VIII provides for the development of **interoperability**, and it includes essential requirements that should facilitate interoperability for data to be reused between sectors.¹²¹ These requirements might be further substantiated through standardisation.

Relevance to In Silico World

If adopted, the Data Act proposal may become relevant for *in silico* technologies. For example, the Data Act could become relevant in a situation of emergency such as a pandemic. On the one hand, private entities qualifying as data holders may be subject to the obligation to share or give access to data with public health bodies. On the other hand, public healthcare sector bodies may be in the position of asking for access to and receiving health data. As another hypothesis, the Data Act could be relevant for an *in silico* technology qualifying as medical device software. In that case, rules concerning *business to consumer* or *business to business data sharing* may become relevant. A user may be in the place to request access to data, as well as other businesses in certain circumstances. Nevertheless, being the legislative act only in a first proposal stage, it would be appropriate to consider these hypotheses as speculative ones – until the legislative act is approved.

¹¹⁵ See art 20 ‘Exceptional need to use data’.

¹¹⁶ See rec 57: ‘[i]n case of public emergencies, such as public health emergencies, emergencies resulting from environmental degradation and major natural disasters including those aggravated by climate change, as well as human-induced major disasters, such as major cybersecurity incidents [...]’.

¹¹⁷ *ibid*, art 20.

¹¹⁸ *ibid*, art 21.

¹¹⁹ Organisations having commercial undertakings having a decisive influence or which could result in preferential access to the results of the research shall be excluded. See *ibid*, art 21(3).

¹²⁰ See art 15 of the proposal, excluding lett a, ie ‘public emergency’.

¹²¹ Data Act proposal, Explanatory Memorandum, 3.

European Health Data Space proposal

Overview

On 3 May 2022, the European Commission issued the European Health Data Space (EHDS) proposal.¹²² The proposal was preceded by several studies and contributions¹²³ and fulfils the policy agenda set by the ‘Towards a Common European Data Space’ and ‘European Strategy for Data’.

Context and scope

The EHDS introduces **additional rights** and mechanisms designed to complement the natural person’s rights provided under the GDPR in relation to their electronic health data¹²⁴ and it establishes a digital health authority responsible for monitoring rights.¹²⁵ Chapter III includes obligations of economic operators with regard to **Electronic Health Records (HER)** systems. For instance, it sets mandatory self-certification scheme for HER systems¹²⁶ voluntary labelling of wellness applications, and a EU databased where certified HER systems and labelled wellness application will be registered.

Chapter IV of the proposal pursues the objective of facilitating the **secondary use of electronic health data**. It includes and defines a set of data types that can be used for defined purposes as well as prohibited purposes.¹²⁷ Also, the proposal requires Member States to establish a health data access body for secondary use of electronic health data and ensure that electronic data are made available by data holders for data users.¹²⁸ The same Chapter includes provision on **data altruism**;¹²⁹ security of the processing environment¹³⁰, data quality.¹³¹

Furthermore, as described in its subject matter and scope¹³² the proposal establishes mandatory **cross-border infrastructure** for the primary and secondary use of electronic health data. Finally, Chapter VI establishes a **European Health Data Space Board**¹³³.

Relevance to In Silico World

Since the EHDS treats the fundamental issue of the primary and secondary use of health data, the proposal promises to be fundamental relevance for *in silico* medicine.

4. Clinical Trials

Introduction

Amongst the barriers to the uptake *in silico* trials, In Silico World Consortium enlists a lack of **clear regulatory pathways** in the EU.¹³⁴ This is especially true when it comes to the regulation of **clinical trials**.¹³⁵ Clinical trials are a kind of clinical studies that investigate the effect of medicinal products on humans – fulfilling one of the following conditions: (a) the assignment of the subject to a particular therapeutic strategy is decided in

¹²² Commission, ‘Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on the European Health Data Space’ COM(2022) 197 final.

¹²³ *ibid*, Section 5; see art 56.

¹²⁴ *ibid*, art 2.

¹²⁵ *ibid*, art 10.

¹²⁶ *ibid*, art 17.

¹²⁷ *ibid*, Explanatory Memorandum.

¹²⁸ *ibid*.

¹²⁹ *ibid*, art 40.

¹³⁰ *ibid*, art 50.

¹³¹ *ibid*, ch 4, sec 5.

¹³² *ibid*, art 1.

¹³³ *ibid*, art 64.

¹³⁴ In Silico World, ‘Barriers to in silico trials’ <https://insilico.world/barriers/> (In Silico World) Accessed 22 March 2022.

¹³⁵ see Avicenna Roadmap, *passim*.

advance and does not fall within the normal clinical practice of the Member State concerned; (b) the decision to prescribe the investigational medicinal products is taken together with the decision to include the subject in the clinical study; or (c) diagnostic or monitoring procedures in addition to normal clinical practice are applied to the subjects.¹³⁶

In its programmatic statements, the In Silico World Consortium underscores there is a **need to explore new regulatory pathways for pharmaceutical products that allow a significant reduction of human experimentation with In Silico Trials technologies** and the adoption of rigorous post-marketing surveillance that monitors the validity of the *in silico* predictions as the new product is adopted.¹³⁷ The exploration of regulatory pathways also starts from the legal framework analysis. This section will illustrate the legal framework of clinical trials.

Legal Framework

The Declaration of Helsinki

Overview

The **Declaration of Helsinki (DoH)**¹³⁸ is a statement of ethical principles to guide medical research involving human subjects, including research on identifiable human material and data. The declaration was adopted in 1964 by the World Medical Association (WMA),¹³⁹ an international and independent association of professional medical associations representing physicians worldwide. The document followed seven amendments until the most recent of October 2013. The declaration is mainly addressed to physicians. The WMA encourages others involved in medical research involving human subjects to adopt these principles.¹⁴⁰

Context and scope

Medical research is subject to ethical standards that promote and ensure respect for all human subjects and protect their health and rights.¹⁴¹ Among its **general principles**, the declaration indicates that physicians must consider the ethical, legal and regulatory norms and standards for research involving human subjects in their own countries and the applicable international norms and standards.

It is the duty of the physician to promote and safeguard the health, well-being and rights of patients, including those who are involved in medical research.¹⁴² Furthermore, it is the duty of physicians who are involved in medical research to protect the life, health, dignity, integrity, right to self-determination, privacy, and confidentiality of personal information of research subjects.¹⁴³ Medical research involving human subjects may only be conducted if the importance of the objective outweighs the risks and burdens to the research subjects.¹⁴⁴ The Declaration adds specific safeguards for research subjects' **privacy and confidentiality**.¹⁴⁵

The declaration offers guidelines on scientific requirements, **research protocol and research ethics committees**. The design and performance of each research study involving human subjects must be clearly

¹³⁶ Shortose S, 'Clinical Trials' in Sally Shorthose (ed) Guide to EU Pharmaceutical Regulatory Law (Seventy Edition, Kluwer Law International 2017).

¹³⁷ *ibid*.

¹³⁸ World Medical Association, 'Declaration of Helsinki – Ethical principles for medical research involving human subjects' (*World Medical Association*, 1964, as last amended on 9th July 2018).

¹³⁹ The WMA adopted global policy statements on a range of ethical issues related to medical professionalism, patient care, research on human subjects and public health, see World Medical Association, 'Homepage' <<https://www.wma.net/>> (*World Medical Association*) accessed 22 March 2022.

¹⁴⁰ *ibid*, para 2.

¹⁴¹ *ibid*, para 7.

¹⁴² *ibid*, para 4.

¹⁴³ *ibid*, para 9.

¹⁴⁴ *ibid*, para 16.

¹⁴⁵ *ibid*, para 24.

described and justified in a research protocol.¹⁴⁶ The research protocol must be submitted for consideration, comment, guidance and approval to the concerned research ethics committee before the study begins. Participation by individuals capable of giving **informed consent** as subjects in medical research must be voluntary.¹⁴⁷ Specific attention is given to **information** on the research subject and the methods used to deliver the information. They must also be informed of the right to refuse to participate in the study or to withdraw consent to participate at any time without reprisal.¹⁴⁸ Finally, the guidance determines that every research study involving human subjects must be registered in a publicly accessible database before recruitment of the first subject. Researchers, authors, sponsors, editors and publishers all have ethical obligations with regard to the **publication and dissemination** of the results of research.

Relevance for In Silico World

The Declaration of Helsinki does not have a binding nature. However, its influence is far-reaching. It has inspired the codification of modern medical research laws worldwide and thus in the EU. *In silico* trials technologies in future shall take due account of the principles set out in the Declaration of Helsinki.

The Declaration of Taipei

Overview

The **Declaration of Taipei (DoT)** on Ethical Considerations regarding Health Databases and Biobanks was adopted by the WMA in October 2002. It was last revised in October 2016. The Declaration complements the Declaration of Helsinki, as it aims to address any use of health databases and biobanks excluding individual treatment and is not restricted to research.¹⁴⁹

The Declaration of Taipei was approved after several years of application to the Declaration of Helsinki. The Research evolved after the DoH was adopted, and new practices entailing the collection of data and human specimens for the development of new research strategies and models arose. The WMA acknowledged the potential of such databases and their dangers, which may rely on the potential use and misuse of health databases and biobanks.¹⁵⁰ With the DoT, the WMA aims to balance the rights of individuals giving their tissue or data for research and other purposes based on confidentiality and privacy rules while at the same time recognising that health data has become a potent tool for increasing knowledge.¹⁵¹

Context and scope

Similarly to the DoH, the Declaration of Taipei indicates that physicians must consider the ethical, legal and regulatory norms and standards for Health Database and Biobanks in their own countries as well as applicable international norms and standards. Unlike the DoH, however, the Declaration of Taipei is not limited to research only; they also address public and private entities that use a biobank or health database.

In its first section – **individual rights** – the declaration emphasises respect for dignity, autonomy, privacy and confidentiality of individuals, and ethical and legal requirements. It recognises the rights to autonomy, privacy and confidentiality as entitling individuals to exercise control over the use of their personal data and biological material. The collection, storage and use of data and biological material from individuals capable of giving

¹⁴⁶ *ibid*, para 22.

¹⁴⁷ *ibid*, para 25.

¹⁴⁸ *ibid*, para 26.

¹⁴⁹ According to the DoT, a health database is a system for collecting, organising, and storing health information. A biobank is a collection of biological material and associated data (DoT, para 4).

¹⁵⁰ World Medical Association, 'Declaration of Taipei. Research on Health Databases, Big Data and Biobanks' (*World Medical Association*) < <https://www.wma.net/what-we-do/medical-ethics/declaration-of-taipei/#:~:text=The%20Declaration%20of%20Taipei%20tries,powerful%20tool%20for%20increasing%20knowledge.>> accessed 22 March 2022.

¹⁵¹ *ibid*.

consent must be voluntary. If the data and biological material are collected for a given research project, the participants' specific, free and informed consent must be obtained following the Declaration of Helsinki. In its second section – **governance** – the declaration contains guidelines on mechanisms to govern health databases and biobanks (such as individual protection, transparency, participation and inclusion, and accountability) and enlists the content of governance arrangements.

Relevance for In Silico World

As the Declaration of Taipei concerns the use of health databases, it may become relevant for the use of personal data for specific *in silico* technologies research that will make use of such data.

The Clinical Trials Directive

Overview

Prior to the introduction of the CTD, the EU Member States followed the guidelines issued by the International Conference on Harmonisation of Technical Requirements for the Registration of Pharmaceuticals for Human Use (ICH). However, the practices, methods and standards for the approval of drugs and medical devices were divergent across the Member States. The Clinical Trials Directive was approved in the EU to homogenise the practice happening at the national level concerning clinical trials' execution. The **CTD built on the ICH standards** and detailed how the standards should be incorporated into clinical practice within the EU.

Context and scope

The primary objective of the directive is to set common rules to be implemented at the national level by the Member States to have common rules for the authorisation and regulatory follow up of clinical trials, protect participating humans, and ensure the credibility of results. The Directive applies to all clinical trials, in the EU, except non-interventional clinical trials.¹⁵² The Directive defines the responsibilities of sponsors for clinical trials. Before the clinical trial commencement, **approval** must be sought from the **Competent Authority (CA)** and the **ethics committee** where the trial takes place.¹⁵³ **Ethics committees** shall give their opinion before a clinical trial commences.¹⁵⁴ Approval may be granted if satisfactory information demonstrates the quality of the investigational agent and its non-clinical safety has been provided, unitedly with a protocol detailing how the trial is going to be executed.¹⁵⁵ The sponsor must design the **clinical trial protocol**, which shall describe the objectives, design, methodology, statistical considerations and organisation of the trial.¹⁵⁶ The sponsor also has the duty to put in place a **quality management system**, select an investigator and the institution, and create the investigator's brochure. Also, the sponsor shall take care of the **informed consent** procedure and guarantee the protection of clinical trial subjects¹⁵⁷, including their right to physical and mental integrity, privacy and data protection¹⁵⁸. All trials shall be carried out in accordance with GCP standards, while the manufacturing, labelling and storage of IMPs must comply with Good Manufacturing Practices (GMP).

Relevance for In Silico World

The CTD is a fundamental piece of legislation for *in silico* trials. In Silico World does not envisage the direct involvement of human participants in the project.¹⁵⁹ Nevertheless, future practices for the study of *in silico* technologies are likely to require adherence to clinical trials rules.

¹⁵² CTD, art 2(c).

¹⁵³ CTD, art 9.

¹⁵⁴ CTD, art 6.

¹⁵⁵ Shortose S, 'Clinical Trials' in Sally Shorthose (ed) *Guide to EU Pharmaceutical Regulatory Law* (Seventy Edition, Kluwer Law International 2017), 65.

¹⁵⁶ CTD, art 2(h).

¹⁵⁷ CTD, art 3.

¹⁵⁸ CTD, art 3(2)(c).

¹⁵⁹ see In Silico World, 'D10.1 H – Requirement No. 1, 2' (2021); In Silico World, 'D10.2 – Requirement No. 2' (2021), 3; In Silico World, 'D10.4 – H Requirement No. 3' (2021); In Silico World, 'D10.3 H – Requirement No. 8' (2021).

The Good Clinical Practice Directive

Overview

Directive 2005/28/EC¹⁶⁰ (Good Clinical Practice Directive) governs the conduct of trials for medicinal products for human use, as well as the requirements for authorisation of the manufacturing or importation of such products. The Good Clinical Practice Directive adds to the implementation of the **GCP rules** set out in the Clinical Trials Directive in three respects. First, it defines detailed principles and guidelines of good clinical practice so that all experts and persons involved in the design, initiation, conduct and registration of clinical trials apply the same standards of good clinical practice. Second, it establishes minimum requirements for applications and management of authorizations to manufacture or import investigational medicinal products and the granting and content of authorizations to ensure the quality of the investigational medicinal product used in a clinical trial. Third, it allows the definition in each Member State of provisions for the functioning of the ethics committees on the basis of detailed common guidelines in order to guarantee the protection of the subjects of the trial. This Directive compiles the modalities allowing the facilitation of academic trials under the CTD.

Context and scope

The Directive lays down the **principles of good clinical practice** and detailed guidelines in line with those principles for the design, conduct and reporting of clinical trials on human subjects involving medicinal products. Also, it includes requirements for authorisation of the manufacture or importation of investigational products. The directive offers guidelines on the **documentation** relating to clinical trials, archiving, qualifications of inspectors and inspection procedures. To ensure compliance of clinical trials with the principles of Good Clinical Practice, inspectors must ensure the practical effectiveness of these provisions. The Directive provides minimum standards for the qualification of inspectors, in particular as regards their education and their training. The Directive further details the conditions for the protocol and the investigator's brochure, the cooperation between the ethics committees and the competent authority of the Member State, as well as manufacturing and import requirements. It also sets requirements for the Trial Master File (TMF) and archiving.

Relevance for In Silico World

As part of the legislative framework of clinical trials, the Good Clinical Practice Directive is relevant to the In Silico World project. Analysis of it jointly with the other pieces of legislation, is necessary to overcome the regulatory barriers to the uptake of *in silico* trials.

The Clinical Trials Regulation

Overview

As mentioned above, notwithstanding the objective of the Clinical Trial Directive was to harmonise the legislation of clinical trials in the EU, the scattered approaches by the Member States and administrative constraints posted by its scope and procedures led to criticism of the Directive. The Directive was criticised in the academic domain for not being fit for the needs of academia compared to those of the pharmaceutical industry, its regulatory costs and complexity of procedures for academic researchers.¹⁶¹ In April 2014, with the objective of harmonising the rules, the European Parliament and the Council adopted the Clinical Trial Regulation.

¹⁶⁰ Commission Directive 2005/28/EC of 8 April 2005 laying down principles and detailed guidelines for good clinical practice as regards investigational medicinal products for human use, as well as the requirements for authorisation of the manufacturing or importation of such products [2005] OJ L91/13 (Good Clinical Trial Directive or GCP Directive).

¹⁶¹ Abou-el-Enein M and others, 'Deciphering the EU clinical trials regulation' (2016) 34 Nature Biotechnology <<https://www.nature.com/articles/nbt.3492>> accessed 22 March 2022, 1.

In 2012, the European Commission put forward the proposal for a Clinical Trials Regulation to replace the former Clinical Trial Directive. **Regulation 536/2014 (Clinical Trials Regulation)**¹⁶² entered into force on 16 June 2014 and became applicable on 31 January 2022. Its objective is to ensure a greater level of harmonisation for the rules concerning the conduction of clinical trials across the EU. In addition, it aims to strengthen the coordination within and between the Member States and support the conduct of multi-country trials as well as ensure the production of reliable and robust, high level scientific data and ensure participant safety. A **transition period** is foreseen for its application. From 31 January 2022 to January 2023, sponsors may submit clinical trials under the legal framework of CTD or CTR. From 31 January onwards, all clinical trial applications will be subject to CTR – trials approved under CTD before that date can continue to follow CTD rules until 31 January 2025. As of 31 January, all clinical trials shall follow the CTR rules.

Context and scope

The scope of the new Regulation is, in essence, equivalent to that of the Clinical Trials Directive. The regulation concerns clinical research on medicinal products, and it does not apply to non-interventional studies.¹⁶³ The elements of innovation brought by the CTR are many. The CTR laid out the rules for an **authorisation procedure based on a single submission** via a single EU portal, the Clinical Trials Information System (CTIS).¹⁶⁴ In order to facilitate cross-country clinical trials, the CTR introduced a **harmonised procedure** for the assessment of applications for clinical trials, which is divided into two parts.¹⁶⁵ Part I shall be jointly assessed by all Member States concerned (where the trial is intended to be conducted); Part II is assessed by every MS concerned separately. Also, the CTR renovates rules on the involvement of **ethics committees** in the assessment procedure in accordance with national law.¹⁶⁶ There are new rules on **transparency** about clinical trials and their outcomes.¹⁶⁷ Finally, the regulation adds further controls in the Member States and third countries to ensure that clinical trials are properly supervised and enforced.¹⁶⁸

Relevance for In Silico World

Similarly to the CTD, the CTR is of core importance for *in silico* trials. In Silico World does not envisage direct involvement of human participants in the project.¹⁶⁹ Nevertheless, future practices for the study of *in silico* technologies may require adherence to clinical trial rules.

5. Medical Devices and Medicinal Products

Introduction

The In Silico World project envisages to develop a set of solutions targeting different specialities (endocrinology, orthopaedics, infectiology, neurology, oncology, cardiology) and diseases (osteoporosis, dynapenia-sarcopenia, osteoarthritis, tuberculosis, multiples sclerosis, mammary carcinoma, arterial stenosis, cerebral aneurisms), and different types of medical products. Notably, from a product regulation perspective, these solutions may under certain circumstances qualify as **medical devices, medicinal products, or Advanced Therapeutic Medicinal Products (ATMP)**.

¹⁶² Regulation (EU) No 536/2014 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 16 April 2014 on clinical trials on medicinal products for human use, and repealing Directive 2001/20/EC [2014] OK L158/1 (Clinical Trials Regulation or CTR).

¹⁶³ CTR, art 1.

¹⁶⁴ CTR, art 5, art 80.

¹⁶⁵ see CTR, rec 4.

¹⁶⁶ CTR, art 4.

¹⁶⁷ see CTR, recs 25 and 67.

¹⁶⁸ see CTR, chapter XIII.

¹⁶⁹ see In Silico World, 'D10.1 H – Requirement No. 1', (2021), 2; In Silico World, 'D10.2 – Requirement No. 2' (2021), 3; In Silico World, 'D10.4 – H Requirement No. 3' (2021); In Silico World, 'D10.3 H – Requirement No. 8' (2021).

To support the analysis of possible regulatory pathways for the uptake of *in silico* trials, it is therefore essential to draw the fundamentals of existing healthcare and sector-specific product legislation as applicable to the tangible and intangible objects in the scope of the project. The following sections will therefore analyse the EU framework on medical devices (with a focus on the Medical Device Regulation¹⁷⁰ and In Vitro Diagnostic Regulation¹⁷¹), medicinal products (having regard to the Community Code for Medicinal Products for Human Use¹⁷², Regulation 726/2004¹⁷³), advanced therapeutic medicinal products regulation in the EU¹⁷⁴, and Regulation 2021/2282 on Health Technology Assessment (HTAR)¹⁷⁵.

Legal Framework (Medical Devices)

Medical devices have been subject to EU regulation for many years as part of product safety legislation. The first EU-wide legal framework on medical devices legal consisted of **three Directives** (Council Directive 90/385/EEC on Active Implantable Medical Devices¹⁷⁶, Council Directive 93/42/EEC on Medical Devices,¹⁷⁷ and Council Directive 98/79/EC on In Vitro Diagnostic Medical Devices¹⁷⁸). These were recently reformed as they seem no longer reflect scientific and technological progress. At the same time, they seemed too focused on the route towards CE-marking while there were not enough sufficient controls to ensure their safety and effectiveness.¹⁷⁹ The current legal framework in the EU aiming at ensuring a high level of quality for medical devices and guaranteeing the protection of human health and safety is composed of two Regulations: Regulation 2017/745 (**Medical Device Regulation**) and Regulation 2017/746 (**In Vitro Diagnostic Regulation**). The first applies to medical devices, while the second concerns in vitro diagnostic medical devices.

The new set of rules of the **MDR** contains several **elements of innovation**.¹⁸⁰ As the European Commission put it, the regulation includes stricter ex-ante control for high-risk devices via a new pre-market scrutiny mechanism with the involvement of **expert panels** at the EU level¹⁸¹; the reinforcement of the criteria for

¹⁷⁰ Regulation (EU) 2017/745 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 April 2017 on medical devices, amending Directive 2001/83/EC, Regulation (EC) No 178/2002 and Regulation (EC) No 1223/2009 and repealing Council Directives 90/385/EEC and 93/42/EEC [2017] OJ L117/1 (MDR).

¹⁷¹ Regulation (EU) 2017/746 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 April 2017 on in vitro diagnostic medical devices and repealing Directive 98/79/EC and Commission Decision 2010/227/EU [2017] OJ L117/176 (IVDR).

¹⁷² Directive 2001/83/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 6 November 2001 on the Community code relating to medicinal products for human use [2001] OJ L311/67.

¹⁷³ Regulation (EC) No 726/2004 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 31 March 2004 laying down Community procedures for the authorisation and supervision of medicinal products for human and veterinary use and establishing a European Medicines Agency [2004] OJ L 136/30.

¹⁷⁴ Regulation (EC) No 1394/2007 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 November 2007 on advanced therapy medicinal products and amending Directive 2001/83/EC and Regulation (EC) No 726/2004 [2007] OJ L324/121 (ATMP Regulation).

¹⁷⁵ Regulation (EU) 2021/2282 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 15 December 2021 on health technology assessment and amending Directive 2011/24/EU (2021) OJ 458/1.

¹⁷⁶ Council Directive of 20 June 1990 on the approximation of the laws of the Member States relating to active implantable medical devices (90/385/EEC) [1990] OJ 189/17 (Directive on implantable medical devices).

¹⁷⁷ Council Directive 93/42/EEC of 14 June 1993 concerning medical devices [1993] OJ 169/43 (Medical Device Directive or MDD).

¹⁷⁸ Directive 98/79/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 October 1998 on in vitro diagnostic medical devices [1998] OJ L331/1.

¹⁷⁹ Verhenneman G, 'Medical Devices Regulations sound the legal future for heart valves and sticking plasters' (*KU Leuven CiTiP Blog*, 6 June 2018) <<https://www.law.kuleuven.be/citip/blog/medical-devices-regulations-sound-the-legal-future-for-heart-valves-and-sticking-plasters/>> accessed 22 March 2022.

¹⁸⁰ Commission, 'Medical Devices – New regulations > Overview' (*European Commission's website*) <https://ec.europa.eu/health/medical-devices-new-regulations/overview_en> accessed 22 March 2022.

¹⁸¹ MDR, art 106 (and art 48 IVDR).

designation and processes for oversight of Notified Bodies (NB)¹⁸²; the inclusion of certain aesthetic devices¹⁸³; improved transparency through the establishment of a **comprehensive EU database on medical devices (MDR EUDAMED)**¹⁸⁴ and of a device traceability system based on Unique Device Identification (UDI)¹⁸⁵; the introduction of an “implant card” containing information about implanted medical devices for a patient¹⁸⁶; the reinforcement of the rules on **clinical evidence**, including an EU-wide coordinated procedure for authorisation of multi-centre clinical investigations;¹⁸⁷ the strengthening of **post-market surveillance** requirements for manufacturers¹⁸⁸.

The **IVDR** introduced substantial changes in the regulatory framework for in vitro diagnostic medical devices. Amongst the key changes, the IVDR has **increased the involvement of notified bodies**,¹⁸⁹ presented a new device **reclassification** rule in line with international guidance, and extended its scope to include diagnostic services (e.g. genetic tests and other tests providing information on the predisposition of patients to develop a disease or on sensitivity to medical therapy)¹⁹⁰.

The provisions of the MDR and IVDR are interpreted at the EU level by the **Medical Device Coordination Group (MDCG)**.¹⁹¹ Health authorities in their respective national territories may provide additional guidance. Finally, other transnational sources are relevant to the framework of EU medical devices. Worth mentioning is the documentation provided by the **International Medical Device Regulators Forum (IMDRF)**, which influences the guidance issued by EU regulators and national authorities, and the documents provided by the **World Health Organisation (WHO)**.

Medical Device Regulation

Overview

The **Medical Device Regulation** entered into force in May 2017 and became directly applicable in the European Union as of 26 May 2021. It replaced the former Directive on Implantable medical devices and the Medical Device Directive. As it is a risk-based regulation,¹⁹² it contains **requirements addressed to manufacturers** for the placing on the market, making available on the market or putting into service of medical devices for human use and accessories for such devices in the Union.¹⁹³

¹⁸² MDR, chapter IV.

¹⁸³ see MDR, rec 12.

¹⁸⁴ Commission, ‘EUDAMED Database’ <<https://ec.europa.eu/tools/eudamed/#/screen/home>> accessed 24 May 2022.

¹⁸⁵ MDR, art 2(15).

¹⁸⁶ MDR, art 18.

¹⁸⁷ MDR, art 78.

¹⁸⁸ MDR, chapter VII.

¹⁸⁹ In fact, under Directive 98/79/EC a small number of high-risk devices was subject to notified body control. While with the new regulation was estimated that around 80% of in vitro diagnostic medical devices would be under the control of notified bodies, the majority of them will be for the first time. See MedTech, ‘MedTech Europe Survey Report analysing the availability of In vitro Diagnostic Medical Devices (IVDs) in May 2022 when the new EU IVD Regulation applies’ (8 September 2021) <<https://www.medtecheurope.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/09/medtech-europe-survey-report-analysing-the-availability-of-in-vitro-diagnostic-medical-devices-ivds-in-may-2022-when-the-new-eu-ivd-regulation-applies-8-september-2021.pdf>> accessed 22 March 2022, 2.

¹⁹⁰ IVDR, art 2.

¹⁹¹ Formerly, medical devices’ rules were interpreted by MEDDEV.

¹⁹² For further contextualisation and elaboration about risk-regulation theories applied to the medical devices’ product sector, see Wilkinson A, ‘Medical Device Regulation and Litigation: A Comparative Analysis of Australia, the United Kingdom and the United States of America’ (DPhil thesis, Queensland University of Technology, 2021).

¹⁹³ MDR, art 1.

Context and scope

Medical devices are **defined in the MDR** as ‘any instrument, apparatus, appliance, software, implant, reagent, material or other article intended by the manufacturer to be used, alone or in combination, for human beings for one or more of the following specific medical purposes: (i) diagnosis, prevention, monitoring, prediction, prognosis, treatment or alleviation of disease; (ii) diagnosis, monitoring, treatment, alleviation of, or compensation for, an injury or disability; (iii) investigation, replacement or modification of the anatomy or of a physiological or pathological process or state; (iv) providing information by means of in vitro examination of specimens derived from the human body, including organ, blood and tissue donations, and which does not achieve its principal intended action by pharmacological, immunological or metabolic means, in or on the human body, but which may be assisted in its function by such means’.¹⁹⁴

Manufacturers need to meet several requirements set by the MDR before medical devices can be put on the market. The MDR requires them to have systems for **risk management**¹⁹⁵ and **quality management**.¹⁹⁶ Manufacturers shall conduct **clinical evaluations**,¹⁹⁷ compile **technical documentation**,¹⁹⁸ and apply a **conformity assessment procedure**.¹⁹⁹ Manufacturers shall be responsible for their devices once they are on the market.²⁰⁰ Every manufacturer must have appointed a person responsible for regulatory compliance.²⁰¹

When medical devices are put on market, the **CE mark** has to be provided as a proof of certification²⁰². The CE marking require several processes starting from the manufacturer’s choice of the conformity assessment procedures, depending on the **classification** of the medical device.²⁰³ Based on criteria such as intended use, length of time used, interaction with human body and other technical characteristics,²⁰⁴ the device is evaluated with regard to its degree of risk. Annex IX of MDR and ad hoc guidance illustrate classification rules that allow medical devices to be individually placed in one of four classes: Class I, IIa, IIb, and III, whereas class III is the highest risk class).²⁰⁵ **Notified bodies** have a supervisory role and assess the conformity of medical devices to the MDR rules before they are placed on the market.

Relevance to In Silico World

At least three products being designed in the In Silico World may qualify as medical devices, in principle. These are InSole, ISR3D, and UISS-MS. Adherence to legislation on medical devices is consequently necessary and shall be closely monitored by the relevant Consortium partners.

¹⁹⁴ MDR, art 2(1). The same paragraph specifies: ‘The following products shall also be deemed to be medical devices: — devices for the control or support of conception; — products specifically intended for the cleaning, disinfection or sterilisation of devices as referred to in Article 1(4) and of those referred to in the first paragraph of this point’.

¹⁹⁵ MDR, art 10(2).

¹⁹⁶ MDR, art 10(9).

¹⁹⁷ MDR, art 10(3).

¹⁹⁸ MDR, art 10(4).

¹⁹⁹ MDR, art 10(6).

²⁰⁰ MDR, art 10(12)-(14).

²⁰¹ MDR, art 15.

²⁰² MDR, Annex V.

²⁰³ see MDR, Annex VIII.

²⁰⁴ Rules on classification have been interpreted over time via ad hoc guidance, see Medical Device Coordination Group ‘MDCG 2019-11 Qualification and classification of software – Regulation (EU) 2017/745 and Regulation (EU) 2017/746’ (2019). For an example of application of the guidance, see Kamenjasevic E and Biasin E, ‘A Commentary on Contact Proximity Tracing Apps in the Context of the EU Legal Framework for Medical Devices’ (2020) 4 European Pharmaceutical Law Review <https://doi.org/10.21552/eplr/2020/2/8>.

²⁰⁵ idem.

In Vitro Medical Device Regulation

Overview

The **In Vitro Medical Device Regulation** replaces Directive 98/79/EC on in vitro diagnostic medical devices was planned to apply as from May 2022. However, the extraordinary circumstances caused by COVID19 implied a higher demand of substantial additional resources and increased availability of in vitro diagnostic medical devices, that could not reasonably have been anticipated at the time of adoption of IVDR.²⁰⁶ Therefore, given the shortage of notified body capacity, the European Commission proposed and obtained the delay of certain provisions of the Regulation.²⁰⁷

Context and scope

In Vitro Medical Devices **are defined by the IVDR** as ‘any medical device which is a reagent, reagent product, calibrator, control material, kit, instrument, apparatus, piece of equipment, software or system, whether used alone or in combination, intended by the manufacturer to be used in vitro for the examination of specimens, including blood and tissue donations, derived from the human body, solely or principally for the purpose of providing information on one or more of the following: (a) concerning a physiological or pathological process or state; (b) concerning congenital physical or mental impairments; (c) concerning the predisposition to a medical condition or a disease; (d) to determine the safety and compatibility with potential recipients; (e) to predict treatment response or reactions; (f) to define or monitoring therapeutic measures’.²⁰⁸ Examples of IVMD include HIV tests, pregnancy tests or SARS-CoV-2 tests. The IVDR introduced a **rules-based classification system** for IVDs. IVDs may be classified into four different classes based on risk class – from class A (low) to class D (high).

Analogously to the MDR, the IVDR’s objective is to lay down rules concerning the placing on the market, making available in the market or putting into services in vitro medical devices for human use. As the MDR, conformity assessment of IVDs are subject to the **classification** of the devices. Classes B, C, D will require an **assessment** and **certification** by a notified body for medical devices prior to being placed on the market. Manufacturers shall carry out **performance evaluation** and performance studies for IVD devices. The devices must be respect general **safety and performance requirements**, including for labelling, technical documentation and quality management systems. Manufacturers shall respect rules **post-market surveillance and vigilance**.

Relevance to In Silico World

In the current state of works, In Silico World solutions do not fall under the scope of IVDR, and therefore the said Regulation is not practically relevant within the project. This section, nevertheless, was added for the sake of completeness and for suggesting that future in vitro medical device technologies developed *in silico* shall take into consideration IVDR rules.

Legal Framework (Medicinal Products)

Community Code for Medicinal Products for Human Use

Context and scope

Directive 2001/83 on the Community code relating to medicinal products for human use (Code Directive) is the most important Directive concerning medicinal products for human use. This Directive outlines the fundamental principles for putting a medicinal product on the market.

²⁰⁶ IVDR, rec 2.

²⁰⁷ Regulation (EU) 2022/112 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 25 January 2022 amending Regulation (EU) 2017/746 as regards transitional provisions for certain in vitro diagnostic medical devices and the deferred application of conditions for in-house devices (Text with EEA relevance) [2022] OJ L19/3.

²⁰⁸ IVDR, art 2.

Overview

The scope of the application of the Directive includes industrially produced medicinal products for human use. Medicinal products for human use are defined by the Directive as:

- a) Any substance or combination of substances presented as having properties for treating or preventing disease in human beings; or
- b) Any substance or combination of substances which may be used in or administered to human beings either with a view to restoring, correcting or modifying physiological functions by exerting a pharmacological, immunological or metabolic action, or to making a medical diagnosis.²⁰⁹

The Directive establishes rules and procedures for marketing authorisation of medicinal products and their monitoring in the EU. It does not include in its scope medicinal products prepared in a pharmacy or intended for research and development trials, intermediate products intended for further processing by an authorised manufacturer, radionuclides in the form of sealed sources.²¹⁰

Regulation 726/2004 on authorisation procedures and establishing EMA

Context and scope

Regulation 726/2004 laying down Union procedures for the authorisation and supervision of medicinal products for human use and establishing a European Medicines Agency was approved in 2004 and came into force in 2005 and 2008.²¹¹ The Regulation lays down **procedures for the authorisation, supervision and pharmacovigilance of medicinal products for human use** in the EU. Also it established the European Medicines Agency (EMA).²¹²

Overview

The first part of Regulation 726/2004 sets procedural rules for the authorisation of certain medicinal products that require central authorisation procedure for their market authorisation.²¹³ Chapter 1 of Title II notably, set out the rules the submission and examination of applications and authorisation procedures. Marketing authorisation granted following this Regulation is valid throughout the Union and confers the same rights and obligations in each of the Member States as a marketing authorisation granted by that Member State.²¹⁴

The second part of Regulation 726.2004 concerns the **establishment of the European Medicines Agency** (EMA). The Agency is responsible for coordinating the existing scientific resources put at its disposal by Member States for the evaluation, supervision and pharmacovigilance of medicinal products for human use and of veterinary medicinal products.²¹⁵

Relevance to In Silico World

Requirements stemming from this Regulation may be relevant to the stakeholders that aim at placing medicinal products that are developed through *in silico* technologies falling under the scope of this Regulation.

Advanced Therapeutic Medicinal Products Regulation

Overview

Scientific progresses in the field of cellular and molecular technology led to the development of an increased number of ATMPs. **Regulation 1394/2007 (Advanced Therapeutic Medicinal Products Regulation)** represents the fundamental piece of legislation for ATMP in the EU. The Regulation came into force on 30 December 2008

²⁰⁹ Directive 2001/83, art 1(2). See also Georgiev N et al, 'PharmaLedger D5.1 Ethical and Legal Inventory' (2021).

²¹⁰ *ibid*, art 2.

²¹¹ Regulation 726/2004, art 90.

²¹² *ibid*, art 2.

²¹³ *ibid*, art 10.

²¹⁴ *ibid*, art 13.

²¹⁵ *ibid*, art 55.

and modified Directive 2001/83²¹⁶ and Regulation 726/2004, laying down Community procedures for the authorisation and supervision of medicinal products for human and veterinary use.²¹⁷

Context and scope

The ATMP Regulation includes four main sub-categories of advanced therapeutic medicinal products: gene therapy; somatic cell therapy, tissue therapies, combined advanced therapies.²¹⁸ Similarly to any other medicinal product, the development of ATMPs shall be in compliance with the Good Clinical Practice Directive and legislation on clinical trials. The development of advanced therapies in the EU requires the individual submission to the national competent authority where the trial will take place. All advanced therapy medicines are subject to a marketing authorisation, granted through a **centralised evaluation and authorisation procedure**.

Two committees are responsible for the validation and scientific evaluation of product approval: the EMA's Committee for Medicinal Products for Human Use (CHMP), and the Committee for Advanced Therapies (CAT). In fact, as the complexity of ATMPs require specific skills – and sometimes evaluation criteria go beyond those present in the traditional pharmaceutical sector, the EMA set up a Committee for Advanced Therapies (CAT). The main responsibility of the CAT is to prepare a draft opinion on each application for marketing authorisation of ATMP, to be submitted to EMA in order to support the final decision by the CHMP. The CAT may also offer confirmation that a medicine qualifies as a ATMP. When relevant, the CAT interacts with national notified bodies as regulatory authorities in charge of medical devices. ATMPs are not only regulated by guidelines concerning medicinal products, but also those concerning medical devices. Directive 2009/120/EC updated the definitions and detailed scientific and technical requirements for advanced therapies.

Relevance to In Silico World

In silico trials may also concern the development of ATMPs. 'OcDefects' – a mechanobiology model of osteochondral cartilage regeneration process to be used for *in silico* trials of an ATMP for the repair of deep osteochondral defects – is being developed in the context of In Silico World, to which ATMP rules may be of relevance.

Health Technology Assessment Regulation

Overview

Regulation 2021/2282 on Health Technology Assessment (HTAR)²¹⁹ was proposed by the European Commission on 31 January 2018. **Health Technology Assessment** as a multidisciplinary process that summarises information about the medical, patient and social aspects and the economic and ethical issues related to the use of a health technology. Its aim is to inform the formulation of safe, effective health policies that are patient focused and seek to achieve best value.²²⁰

Before the HTAR, all Member States already established HTA processes at national and regional levels – they had 51 HTA bodies established in 26 Member States, using different assessment methodologies.²²¹ In light of

²¹⁶ Directive 2001/83/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 6 November 2001 on the Community code relating to medicinal products for human use [2001] OJ 311/67.

²¹⁷ Regulation (EC) No 726/2004 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 31 March 2004 laying down Community procedures for the authorisation and supervision of medicinal products for human and veterinary use and establishing a European Medicines Agency [2004] OJ L136/1.

²¹⁸ ATMP Regulation, art 2(1).

²¹⁹ Regulation (EU) 2021/2282 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 15 December 2021 on health technology assessment and amending Directive 2011/24/EU (2021) OJ 458/1.

²²⁰ *ibid*, 4.

²²¹ Commission, 'Commission Staff Working Document. Impact Assessment. Strengthening of the EU Cooperation on Health Technology Assessment (HTA). Accompanying the document Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on health technology assessment and amending Directive 2011/24/EU' SWD(2018) 41 final, 16.

these problems and with the objective to achieve a higher level of harmonisation across Europe, the EU legislator deemed appropriate to establish a commonly agreed regulation in the matter of HTAs. The Regulation was adopted in November 2021, and after the a transitional period of three years for the EU Member States it will be directly applicable as of January 2025.

Context and scope

The objective of HTAR is to set **rules and methodologies for the assessment of health technologies in the EU**. A first part of the regulation establishes the four pillars for the cooperation of Member States at Union level, which are the joint clinical assessments, the joint scientific consultations, the identification of emerging health technologies and voluntary cooperation. Further, the Regulation establishes a mechanism which lays down that any information, data, analyses and other evidence required for the joint clinical assessment of health technologies is to be submitted by the health technology developer only once at Union level. A final part is dedicated to the support framework and procedures for cooperation of Member States on health technologies at Union level.

Relevance to In Silico World

HTA focuses specifically on the added value of a health technology in comparison with other new existing health technologies,²²² and as such, might be relevant to in silico trials of medicinal products or medical devices. Nevertheless, direct application of the Regulation is due at January 2025, before which the European Commission and the HTA Coordination Group is expected to provide additional implementative guidance. The monitoring of these steps will therefore be useful in the months to come.

6. Artificial Intelligence

In silico technologies entail the use of Artificial Intelligence. For example, AI-powered *in silico* trials may enable researchers to adapt quickly to a large computer environment, transforming large data sets to better understand drug response, predict outcomes and discover new drug indications.²²³ Furthermore, Computer Modelling and Simulation (CM&S) combined with AI are deemed effective tools to innovate research and development processes in healthcare.²²⁴

The EU does not have a comprehensive legal framework for Artificial Intelligence yet. Nevertheless, the fast development of AI-powered technologies made regulation of Artificial Intelligence a central policy question in the European Union. Initially, the European Commission adopted a soft law approach. In 2019, it published the **Ethics Guidelines on Trustworthy AI**²²⁵ and its **Policy and Investment Recommendations**.²²⁶ However, with its Communication on Fostering a European approach to Artificial Intelligence²²⁷, the European Commission showed its intention to shift toward a legislative strategy and called to build a proportionate and risk-based European regulatory approach.²²⁸ In 2020, the European Commission issued its **White Paper on**

²²² HTAR, rec 2.

²²³ Fassbender M, 'How in silico trials are making personalized medicine a reality' (*Outsourcing-Pharma.com* 2019) <[https://www.outsourcing-pharma.com/Article/2019/01/02/How-in-silico-trials-are-making-personalized-medicine-a-reality#:~:text=Powered%20by%20artificial%20intelligence%20\(AI,and%20discover%20new%20drug%20indications](https://www.outsourcing-pharma.com/Article/2019/01/02/How-in-silico-trials-are-making-personalized-medicine-a-reality#:~:text=Powered%20by%20artificial%20intelligence%20(AI,and%20discover%20new%20drug%20indications)> accessed 22 March 2022.

²²⁴ In Silico Trials, 'Our Approach' (*In Silico Trials*) <<https://insilicotrials.com/our-approach/>>, accessed 22 March 2022.

²²⁵ see *infra*.

²²⁶ High Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence, 'Policy and Investment Recommendations for Trustworthy AI' (2019).

²²⁷ Commission, 'Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of Regions. Fostering a European Approach to Artificial Intelligence' COM(2021) 205 final.

²²⁸ *ibid*, 6.

Artificial Intelligence²²⁹. There, the Commission repeated the necessity to have a regulatory approach for promoting the uptake of AI and addressing the risk associated with certain uses of this technology.²³⁰ Finally, in April 2021, the Commission put forward a **proposal**²³¹ for the horizontal regulation of Artificial Intelligence, focusing on the specific use for AI systems and their associated risks.

Legal Framework

The AI Act Proposal

Overview

On April 21, the European Commission presented the **Artificial Intelligence Act (AI Act)**.²³² The proposed legislative act represents the effort of the EU to regulate AI and it is the first horizontal legislative proposal on the matter in the EU. Previous to it, the EU policy-making landscape was prepared by the issuance of other relevant documents, such as the Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI, issued by the High-Level Expert Group on AI (in December 2018), the White Paper on AI (Issued by the EC in February 2020), and the European Parliament's framework of ethical aspects of AI, robotics and related technologies as of October 2020.²³³

Context and scope

The AI Act sets horizontal rules for placing on the market, putting into service and **using AI systems** in the Union. It prohibits certain AI practices and introduces specific requirements for high-risk AI systems and obligations for operators of such systems. The regulation defines and classifies AI systems according to their risks **to fundamental rights**, and it establishes a list of **prohibited AI practices** following a risk-based approach.

The proposal differentiates between AI that could entail unacceptable risk, high risk and low or minimal risk to individuals' fundamental rights. Prohibited practices comprise all those AI systems whose use is considered unacceptable as posing risks to individuals' fundamental rights as core values of the EU. **The AI Act expressly identifies medical devices as high-risk AI systems.**²³⁴ For high-risk systems to be placed on the EU market, manufacturers will have to adopt a risk management system for the entire lifecycle of the system²³⁵ and comply with several requirements in relation to data and data governance²³⁶, documentation and record-keeping²³⁷, transparency and provision of information to users²³⁸, human oversight²³⁹, robustness, accuracy and security²⁴⁰. Amongst these, data sets used for training, testing and validation of AI systems shall adhere to quality criteria, and they shall be free of errors and complete. Providers shall also maintain detailed technical **documentation**, including system architecture, algorithmic design and model specifications. **Transparency** rules require high-risk AI systems to be designed and developed in such a way to ensure that

²²⁹ Commission, 'White Paper on Artificial Intelligence – A European approach to excellence and trust' COM(2020) 65 final.

²³⁰ Madięga T, 'Artificial Intelligence Act' (European Parliamentary Research Service, 2022) <[https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2021/698792/EPRS_BRI\(2021\)698792_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2021/698792/EPRS_BRI(2021)698792_EN.pdf)>.

²³¹ Commission, 'Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council laying down harmonised rules on Artificial Intelligence (Artificial Intelligence Act) and amending certain Union legislative acts' COM(2021) 206 final.

²³² *ibid.*

²³³ European Parliament, 'Framework of ethical aspects of artificial intelligence, robotics and related technologies. European Parliament resolution of 20 October 2020 with recommendations to the Commission on a framework of ethical aspects of artificial intelligence, robotics and related technologies' (2020/2012(INL)).

²³⁴ AI Act proposal, Annex VI. For more elaborations on the application of the AI Act for medical devices, see Biasin E and Kamenjašević E, 'Cybersecurity of Medical Devices: New Challenges Arising from the AI Act and NIS 2 Directive Proposals' [2022] *International Cybersecurity Law Review* <<https://doi.org/10.1365/s43439-022-00054-x/>>.

²³⁵ AI Act proposal, art 9.

²³⁶ *ibid.*, art 10.

²³⁷ *ibid.*, art 11.

²³⁸ *ibid.*, arts 12 and 13.

²³⁹ *ibid.*, art 14.

²⁴⁰ *ibid.*, art 15.

their operation is sufficiently transparent to enable users to interpret the system's output and to use it appropriately. The systems shall be designed and developed in such a way that natural persons can effectively oversee them during the period in which the AI system is in use. Also, the systems shall achieve an appropriate level of **accuracy, robustness and cybersecurity**, and they shall perform consistently in those respects throughout their lifecycle.

Before a high-risk system is put on the market or deployed to service, it must undergo a **conformity assessment procedure**, after which it will be labelled with a **CE marking**.²⁴¹ Obligations also concern post market monitoring. There is a regime of **serious incident reporting**²⁴² to national authorities and possible corrective actions.²⁴³

Relevance to In Silico World

As explained above, medical device software may fall under the definition of a high-risk AI system under the AI Act proposal. If approved, the AI Act may become relevant for *in silico*-developed technologies.

The Ethics Guidelines on Trustworthy AI

Overview

Since its Communication of 25 April 2018²⁴⁴ and 7 December 2018²⁴⁵, the European Commission has shown the intention to set an ethical and legal framework to support 'ethical, secure and cutting-edge AI made in Europe'²⁴⁶. The High Level Expert Group on AI was composed by a pool of 52 experts to provide guidance and tool that could help practitioners and all, in general, AI stakeholders in implementing ethical principles in practice.

The document envisages **three components** for 'Trustworthy AI', which should be met throughout the system's entire life cycle. The system should be **lawful** – in compliance with all applicable laws and regulations; **ethical** – aligned with ethical principles and values; and **robust** – from a technical and social perspective.²⁴⁷ The Guidelines set out a framework for the achievement of 'Trustworthy AI' by offering guidance on the second two aspects.

Context and scope

In its first chapter, the Guidelines set out the **ethical principles** rooted to EU fundamental rights, to which the development and deployment of AI systems should adhere to.²⁴⁸ These include respect for **human autonomy, prevention of harm, fairness and explicability**.²⁴⁹

Further, in Chapter II, the Guidelines identify **seven** non-exhaustive **requirements** that AI systems should meet. AI systems should envisage the following:²⁵⁰

²⁴¹ *ibid*, art 19.

²⁴² *ibid*, art 62.

²⁴³ *ibid*, chapter III.

²⁴⁴ Commission, 'Communication from the Commission. Artificial Intelligence for Europe' COM(2018) 237 final.

²⁴⁵ Commission, 'Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the European Council, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of Regions. Coordinated Plan on Artificial Intelligence' COM(2018) 795 final.

²⁴⁶ *ibid*.

²⁴⁷ High Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence, 'Ethics Guidelines on Trustworthy AI' (2019).

²⁴⁸ *ibid*, 2.

²⁴⁹ These principles partially overlap with the Biomedical Ethics principles. For a broader discussion of ethical principles, see *infra*.

²⁵⁰ High Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence, 'Ethics Guidelines on Trustworthy AI' (European Commission, 2019), 14.

- **Human agency and oversight**, including fundamental rights, human agency and human oversight.
- **Technical robustness and safety**, including resilience to attack and security, fallback plan and general safety, accuracy, reliability and reproducibility.
- **Privacy and data governance**, including the respect for privacy, quality and integrity of data, and access to data.
- **Transparency**, including traceability, explainability and communication.
- **Diversity, non-discrimination and fairness**, including the avoidance of unfair bias, accessibility and universal design, and stakeholder participation.
- **Environmental and societal well-being**, Including sustainability and environmental friendliness, social impact, society and democracy.
- **Accountability**, Including auditability, minimisation and reporting of negative impact, trade-offs and redress.²⁵¹

The principles should be continuously evaluated and addressed throughout the AI system’s life cycle. In 2020, the High-Level Expert Group issued an **Assessment List for Trustworthy AI (ALTAI)**²⁵² with the objective to help assess whether an AI system may adhere to the above seven requirements of Trustworthy AI.

Relevance to In Silico World

The Ethics guidelines on Trustworthy AI and ALTAI may provide a valuable baseline for assessing whether technology may be considered ‘trustworthy’. Some of the technologies in In Silico World may be considered AI systems, and therefore, the above principles may turn helpful in their development.

7. Ethics Principles

Introduction

Legislation may cover a wide range of themes and address several issues. However, individuals' decision-making and, ultimately, the processes of technologies driven by individual’s values may be influenced by ethical guidelines – as a system of moral principles.

Ethical requirements can support and **motivate** stakeholders to ensure the protection and promotion of human values. While legal frameworks set the formal requirements for individuals and entities, ethical requirements may serve as **drivers of what is indicated by the law**. Moral considerations may help shaping the actions of people, setting constraints and offering guidance for the development of technologies.

In addition, **ethics may underpin laws**. Legislation is often based on ethical problems. For example, informed consent, privacy and confidentiality may be linked to the autonomy principle (*infra*). Anti-discrimination law may be seen as consequently linked to the principle of justice (*infra*). However, regardless how much the law tries to support ethical concerns, it may never prevent morally undesirable consequences from happening.²⁵³

²⁵¹ *ibid.*

²⁵² High Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence, ‘The Assessment List For Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence (ALTAI)’ (European Commission 2020).

²⁵³ Verhenneman G, Vedder A ‘WITDOM "empowering privacy and security in non-trusted environments", D6.2 – Legal requirements on privacy, data protection and security in WITDOM scenarios’ (30 November 2016) 57 <<http://www.witdom.eu/deliverables>>, 63.

Some technologies, like nuclear power, cars, or plastics, have generated ethical discussions and significant policy efforts to control the trajectory these technologies, usually only once some damage is done.²⁵⁴ By identifying and studying the possible concerns, ethics may also help as a **tool to analyse the risks or benefits of tangible forms of harm** that a novel technology could entail.

This could be the case, for instance, of the use of Artificial Intelligence and its regulation. Ethical studies of AI have underscored possible issues that could be in need of regulation, such as bias and opacity in AI systems – which, to continue the example, led the EU legislator in providing specific requirements about it in the new AI Act proposal. In conclusion, ethics may complement laws, and **help understanding** how to apply laws to hitherto or unfamiliar situations.

Theoretical framework

Given their inherent novelty for society, *in silico* trials require the study of its ethical aspects.²⁵⁵ The ethical analysis applied by WP9 follows a **principlist approach**. Principlism is a normative ethical framework initially designed for practical decision making in healthcare. This kind of approach – which consists of an attempt to bring together the best elements of moral theories compatible with most societal, individual or religious belief systems – is a commonly used ethical approach in healthcare and biomedical science.

This section outlines the existing ‘Biomedical Ethics Principles’ (also known as Beauchamp and Childress’ principles of biomedical ethics)²⁵⁶ that may be relevant for *in silico* trials. The four fundamental principles are the respect for persons and autonomy, the principle of justice, the principle of non-maleficence, and beneficence. Applied in the context of *in silico* technologies, these principles may help identify moral problems related to its development and future use. The following sections outline them briefly.

Biomedical ethics principles

Autonomy

Autonomy is derived from the Greek words *autos* (self) and *nomos* (law, system of rules). In more recent understandings, autonomy has acquired the meaning of self-governance, liberty rights, privacy, individual choice, and freedom of the will.²⁵⁷ Initially, the principle of autonomy was known as the ‘principle of respect for persons’ in the Belmont Report.²⁵⁸ Beauchamp and Childress further expanded it by explaining that to respect an autonomous agent is, at least, to recognise an individual’s right to hold views, make choices and take actions based on personal values and beliefs.²⁵⁹

The principle can be stated as a negative and a positive obligation. Regarding the first, it entails that **‘autonomous actions should not be subjected to controlling constraints by others’**.²⁶⁰ Regarding the second positive obligation, the principle of autonomy means that there should be **‘respectful treatment in disclosing information and fostering autonomous decision making’**.²⁶¹ In healthcare, the principle of autonomy requires healthcare professionals and researchers to provide information to human subjects and make sure about the

²⁵⁴ Müller VC, ‘Ethics of Artificial Intelligence and Robotics’ in Edward N Zalta (ed), The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy (Summer 2021, Metaphysics Research Lab, Stanford University 2021) <<https://plato.stanford.edu/archives/sum2021/entries/ethics-ai/>> accessed 3 June 2022.

²⁵⁵ For a brief overview, see, for instance Leo CG and others, ‘Health Technology Assessment for In Silico Medicine: Social, Ethical and Legal Aspects’ (2022) 19 International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health.

²⁵⁶ Beauchamp TL and Childress JF, Principles of Biomedical Ethics (5th ed., New York : Oxford university press 2001).

²⁵⁷ *ibid.*, 58.

²⁵⁸ National Commission for the Protection of Human Subjects of Biomedical and Behavioral Research, ‘Belmont Report: Ethical Principles and Guidelines for the Protection of Human Subjects of Research, Report of the National Commission for the Protection of Human Subjects of Biomedical and Behavioral Research’ (1978).

²⁵⁹ Beauchamp & Childress, 64.

²⁶⁰ *ibid.*

²⁶¹ *ibid.*

understanding and voluntariness of the human subjects to foster their autonomous decision-making. Following Beauchamp's and Childress' words, examples of substantiation of these principles include the following:

1. 'Tell the truth
2. Respect the privacy of others
3. Protect confidential information
4. Obtain consent for interventions with patients
5. When asked, help others make important decisions'.²⁶²

Non-maleficence

This principle implies an obligation **not to inflict harm on other persons**. In medical ethics, this principle is often coupled with the so-called Hippocratic Oath, consisting of the maxim *Primum non nocere* ('above all or first, do no harm'). In other words, the nonmaleficence principle consists of the norm **one ought not to inflict evil or harm**.²⁶³ The principle differs from the beneficence principle. While the beneficence norms (*infra*) require taking action by helping, preventing, removing harm or promoting good, non-maleficence consists of *intentionally refraining* from actions that may cause harm.²⁶⁴ In addition, non-maleficence obligations also include obligations of not imposing **risks** of harm.

Rules supported by the principle of non-maleficence are enlisted by Beauchamp and Childress as follows:

1. 'Do not kill
2. Do not cause pain or suffering
3. Do not incapacitate
4. Do not cause offence
5. Do not deprive others of the goods of life'²⁶⁵

Beneficence

Moral principles not only impose the autonomous treatment of persons and refrain from harming them it is also required to **contribute to their welfare**. There are two principles of beneficence: positive beneficence and utility. **Positive beneficence** requires agents to provide benefits.²⁶⁶ Utility requires that 'agents balance benefits and drawbacks to produce the best overall results'.²⁶⁷ Examples of rules of positive beneficence, in their most general forms, are identified by Beauchamp and Childress as:

1. 'Protect and defend the rights of others
2. Prevent harm from occurring to others
3. Remove conditions that will cause harm to others
4. Help persons with disabilities
5. Rescue persons in danger'²⁶⁸

²⁶² *ibid*, 65.

²⁶³ *ibid*, 115.

²⁶⁴ *ibid*.

²⁶⁵ *ibid*.

²⁶⁶ *ibid*, 165.

²⁶⁷ *ibid*.

²⁶⁸ *ibid*, 167.

The principle of beneficence may be envisaged as an implicit assumption in the ambit of medical care, as it requires contributing to the person's well-being and helping.²⁶⁹

Justice

The principle of justice emphasizes **fairness and equality among individuals**. It claims that people in similar positions should be treated in a similar manner. Stemming from this assumption, the principle requires distributing benefits, risks, and costs similarly. In its subsequent formulation, the principle is conceived more broadly, and it deals with the distributive stance of justice, thus requiring a fair distribution of goods within society.²⁷⁰

In the context of eHealth, for instance, the principle of justice aims at guaranteeing protection to the individuals from stigmatisation based on their economic or social status or their ethnic origin.²⁷¹ As another example, to respect the principle of ownership and non-discrimination, it is crucial to put measures to avoid the improper, unintended or unlawful sharing of patient data. Such an eventuality could lead to discrimination, and it could cause personal or economic harm to individuals.²⁷²

Secondary principles

Responsibility

The secondary principle of **responsibility** may be derived from the above-illustrated principles.²⁷³

Following this principle, everyone has the duty to fulfil their obligations to the best of their abilities based on fundamental ethical principles or a social or professional role. Responsibility also entails the division of obligations of different actors included in the information system.²⁷⁴

Conclusion

The purpose of the present deliverable was to outline the most relevant pieces of legislation applicable to *in silico* trials. The deliverable analysed several areas of legislation: privacy and data protection, data governance, clinical trials, medical devices and medicinal products, and artificial intelligence. The '**Privacy and Data Protection**' section (section 2) underscored the importance of protecting personal data in the eHealth context, having regard to the EU, international, and transnational laws and guidance. Section 3 on '**Data Governance**' illustrated the evolving framework surrounding the data economy and data sharing in healthcare settings. The legislation presented therein may play an important role in the years to come, as it will introduce new rules concerning the sharing of health data in the EU and beyond. At the core of the deliverable, sections 4 and 5 illustrated the most crucial frameworks for *in silico* trials: **clinical trials, medicinal products and medical device legislation**. Their outline is essential as it will serve as a basis for the future deliverables of WP9, which will aim to study the relevant regulatory pathways for the uptake of *in silico* trials. Section 6 outlined the current state-of-the-art for the regulation of **AI in the EU** and included the EU ethics guidelines promoting the trustworthiness of AI products, processes and services. Finally, as the law is not always fully equipped to deal with moral aspects, the deliverable concludes with an '**Ethics principles**' section (section 7). This section studies the principles of biomedical ethics. The analysis of these principles may help build a reflection on ethics and law with regard to *in silico* trials and their possible impacts on patients, the healthcare environment, and ultimately, society.

²⁶⁹ *ibid.*

²⁷⁰ Verhenneman and Vedder (2016), 57.

²⁷¹ Biasin E and others, 'SAFECARE D3.9 Analysis of Ethics, Privacy and Confidentiality Constraints' (2019) <<https://www.safecare-project.eu/?p=465>>, 67.

²⁷² *ibid.*

²⁷³ Vedder A, Responsibilities for Information on the Internet. In Himma KE, Tavani HT (Eds.), *The Handbook of Information and Computer Ethics*, 2009, pp. 339-359, New Jersey: John Wiley and Sons.

²⁷⁴ Verhenneman, G (2016).

The sections above have provided a **descriptive overview** of the relevant legal framework for *in silico* technologies. In the **next phase** of WP9, the ethical and legal analysis will adopt an **evaluative approach** and will focus on the legal challenges that *in silico* trials could bring (D9.2 and 9.3). In light of these and in **the final phase** of the WP, the study will offer **policy recommendations** (D9.4) to overcome the identified challenges and foster the regulatory uptake of *in silico* trials.

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